

Master's thesis report

Carbon footprint assessment of leather waste adopting different possible treatment technologies using the Umberto tool

Leibniz Universität Hannover
Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodesy
Institute of Sanitary Engineering and Waste Management (ISAH)

Singh, Tushar
10025307

1st Examiner : PD Dr.-Ing. habil. Dirk Weichgrebe
2nd Examiner : Sara Zahedi Nezhad, M.sc.
Supervisor : Dr. Mozhiarasi Velusamy

M.Sc., Water Resources and Environmental Management (WATENV)

Submitted on 01.07.2024

DECLARATION OF CONSENT

Last Name: Singh

First Name: Tushar

Matriculation Number: 10025307

E-mail: tushar.singh@stud.uni-hannover.de

Hereby I declare, that my Master's thesis with the title

Carbon footprint assessment of leather waste adopting different possible
treatment technologies using the Umberto tool.

1. has been developed and written entirely by myself and that I referred to all sources and means that I have used for the development of my work in the corresponding report and presentation,
2. has not been submitted to any other authority to achieve an academic grading and was not published elsewhere.

Further I agree,

3. that my Master's thesis is included into the the library of the Institute of Sanitary Engineering and Waste Management of the Leibniz University Hannover (ISAH), and therefore it will be available to members of the institute,
4. to grant the ISAH the the right of use of the results of my Master's thesis and, in particular, the use of the results, consequential from the institute's existing research contexts, for other scientific purposes,
5. that my Master's thesis can be make available to non-members of the university on request¹ without my prior agreement,
6. that my Master's thesis can be copied in extracts for purposes of teaching and research without my prior agreement and
7. that my Master's thesis can be transmitted to an external provider for plagiarism assessment by using a plagiarism software.

¹ Can be deleted in justified cases.

INSTITUT FÜR SIEDLUNGSWASSERWIRTSCHAFT UND ABFALLTECHNIK
LEIBNIZ UNIVERSITÄT HANNOVER

I received a copy of this declaration.

Hannover, 01.07.2024

Signature _____

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Dyhan', is written over a horizontal line.

Application for Admission to Master's Thesis

as per § 12 Sec. 3 of the Examination Regulations for the WATENV Master's Programme dated 2015-08-25
in the current version

Matriculation No.:	10025307	Please complete in block letters!
Surname, Given Name:	Singh Tushar	Subject Semester: 9
Current Address: (Street, ZIP Code, Place)	Clemensstraße 5, 30169, hannover	Telephone: +4917684218774
E-Mail:	tushar.singh@stud.uni-hannover.de	

I hereby apply for admission to the master's thesis as per § 12 Sec. 3 of the Examination Regulations for the WATENV Master's Programme dated 2015-08-25 in the current version.

I have definitely failed an examination in a comparable degree programme, particularly one of the study courses in civil engineering, water and environmental management, environmental engineering.

yes, in the degree programme: Watenv

- at Leibniz Universität Hannover
 at another university

no

Hannover, 10.11.2023

Student Signature

to be completed by Examination Office:

Admission Requirements:	
Enrolled in Degree Programme	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes / () no
Identity card was available	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes / () no
60 Credit Points	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes / () no
Compulsory modules from first semester passed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> yes / () no

After checking the criteria, the application for admission to the master's thesis will be accepted.

Hannover, 14.11.23 By order: (Stamp, Signature)

Note: The master's thesis module consists of a written composition and a colloquium. The master's thesis has to be delivered within 6 months after assignment. This deadline can only be extended for reasonable grounds. As a rule, the master's thesis has to be evaluated by two examiners within 4 weeks. When delivering the master's thesis, it has to be declared in writing that the thesis has been composed independently and no other than the sources and auxiliary materials specified have been used and all points in the thesis which have been adopted either literally or analogously from other sources have been marked accordingly, and that the thesis has not yet been submitted to an examination office in similar or identical form.

Surname, Given Name SINGH, TUSHAR Matriculation Number 10025307

Before having been admitted to the master's thesis by the Examination Office (see overleaf), neither topic assignment nor start of thesis are permitted.

First Examiner: PD DR.-ING. HABIL. DIRK WEICHGREBE

Second Examiner: SARA ZAHEDI NEZHAD, M.SC.
(At least one of the two examiners must be a professor of the
Faculty of Civil Engineering and Geodetic Science.)

Supervisor: DR. MOZHIARASI VELUSAMY

+49 511 762 3967

@MOZHIARASI@ISAH.UNI-HAMNOVER.DE

Topic of Master's Thesis in German (please complete in block letters)

The Master's thesis is written in English () no () yes (If yes, then the German-language topic is omitted)

Topic of Master's Thesis in English (please complete in block letters)

CARBON FOOTPRINT ASSESSMENT OF LEATHER WASTE
ADOPTING DIFFERENT POSSIBLE TREATMENT
TECHNOLOGIES USING UMBERTO TOOL

Please complete, sign and return both pages of this form to the Examination Office.

Date of the Admission:

14.11.2023

Start date of the Thesis (i. e. Assignment of topic):

01.12.2023

End-date of the Thesis:

01.06.2024

1st Examiner: Date, Signature

Signature of the student

(Confirmation of receipt of the named topic)

Tushar

2nd Examiner: Date, Signature

Zahedi Nezhad

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	viii
List of Tables.....	x
Foreword.....	xii
Abstract.....	xiii
List of Abbreviations.....	xiv
1. Introduction.....	1
2. Literature Review & LCA.....	4
2.1 Leather wastes and their physicochemical parameters from tanneries.....	4
2.2 Possible treatments of leather wastes.....	7
2.2.1 Biological Processes - Anaerobic digestion (AD process).....	7
2.2.2 Biological Processes - Composting.....	9
2.2.3 Thermal Treatment - Pyrolysis.....	9
2.2.4 Thermal Treatment - Incineration.....	10
2.2.5 Open dumping.....	11
2.3 Literature review based upon LCA on leather waste.....	12
3. Materials and Methods.....	19
3.1 Boundary Conditions and Functional Unit.....	19
3.2 Inventories (data collection in Appendix).....	20
3.3 Different solid waste pathways (a sustainable approach).....	21
3.4 Model Development.....	22
4. Results and Discussion.....	24
4.1 Carbon footprint emissions of each scenario.....	24
4.2 Total CFs with Mass and energy recovery (by sustainable approach).....	55
4.2.1 Best combinations for Energy recovery.....	57
4.2.2 Best combinations for complete mass reduction/product recovery.....	59
4.3 Climate change (greenhouse impact).....	61
4.4 Limitations.....	61
5. Conclusion.....	63
6. References.....	67
Publication bibliography.....	67
Appendix.....	74
I. Auxiliary materials.....	74
II. Open dumping emissions.....	75
III. Calculation of specific heat.....	76
IV. Calculation of Moisture removal.....	76
V. Carbon footprint values (Sanitary landfill from literature).....	76
VI. Inventories.....	78

List of Figures

Figure 1. Overview of waste generated by tanneries around the world, and the graph is obtained from POPIȚA et al. (2020).....	2
Figure 2. Current scenario of energy production in India (CEA 2023).....	3
Figure 3. Different types of leather waste (A – G) as shown above on-site visit at Superhouse tannery in Kanpur and Heller leder in Hameln in Lower Saxony.....	6
Figure 4. Comparative view of different parameters for different leather waste (mean), followed by Table 2.....	7
Figure 5. Stages of anaerobic digestion (Grippi et al. 2020).....	8
Figure 6. The general process of composting (aerobic) (Yap and Hadibarata 2022).....	9
Figure 7. Boundary conditions for utilizing leather waste (current study).....	19
Figure 8. Overview of waste treatment hierarchy in order of preference (AlQattan et al. 2018).....	21
Figure 9. The SDGs' goals relate to our current study (United Nations 2019; Oliveira et al. 2024).....	22
Figure 10. Model description for S1- RT-AD as baseline scenario.....	25
Figure 11. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S1- RT-AD.....	26
Figure 12. Contribution of all flows through S1- RT-AD with carbon footprint.....	26
Figure 13. Model description for open dumping for raw trimmings as a baseline scenario for other leather wastes.....	27
Figure 14. Contribution of all processes through S2- RT-LF with carbon footprint.....	28
Figure 15. Model description for S3- RT-GP.....	29
Figure 16. Contribution of all flows through S3- RT-GP with carbon footprint emissions.....	30
Figure 17. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S3- RT-GP.....	30
Figure 18. Model description for S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro.....	32
Figure 19. Contribution of all flows through S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro with carbon footprint emissions.....	33
Figure 20. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro.....	33
Figure 21. Model description for S6-FL-CO.....	34
Figure 22. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S6-FL-CO.....	35
Figure 23. Model description for pyrolysis (Fleshings).....	36
Figure 24. Overview of the amount of emissions emitted from entries in S8-FL-Pyro.....	37
Figure 25. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S8-FL-Pyro.....	37
Figure 26. Model description for biodiesel production (S9-FL-BD).....	38
Figure 27. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in biodiesel.....	39
Figure 28. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in static pile composting of hair waste.....	41

Figure 29. Model description for keratin production from hair waste.....	42
Figure 30. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S12-HW-KP.....	43
Figure 31. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in keratin production.	43
Figure 32. Overview of the amount of emissions emitted from entries in S13-CS-AD.....	45
Figure 33. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S14-CS-AD+Pyro.....	45
Figure 34. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S13-CS-AD & S14-CS-AD+Pyro.....	46
Figure 35. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in S16-CS-Pyro.....	47
Figure 36. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S16-CS-Pyro.....	47
Figure 37. Model description for making leather sheet from chrome shavings & splits.....	48
Figure 38. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in S17-CS-LS.....	49
Figure 39. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in producing leather sheet..	49
Figure 40. Model description for incineration of chrome shavings & splits (S18-CS-INCI).	50
Figure 41. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes.....	51
Figure 42. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in incineration.....	51
Figure 43. Model description for making leather board (S20-BD-BO).....	53
Figure 44. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in leather board.....	54
Figure 45. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in leather board.....	54
Figure 46. Performance of selected scenarios based on the energy recovery.....	57
Figure 47. Mass recovery from as digestate from S1- RT-AD, S4-FL-AD & S13-CS-AD....	59
Figure 48. Mass recovery as biochar from S5-FL-AD+Pyro, S8-FL-Pyro, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S21-BD-Pyro, & S22-FTW-Pyro.....	60
Figure 49. Mass recovery as bio-oil from S5-FL-AD+Pyro, S8-FL-Pyro, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S21-BD-Pyro, & S22-FTW-Pyro.....	60

List of Tables

Table 1. Total amount of leather waste from tanneries.....	4
Table 2. Physical parameters for incoming waste for different waste.....	6
Table 3. Overview of different types of pyrolysis processes for MSW (Varies with utilization of tannery waste) (Jahirul et al. 2012).....	10
Table 4. Emissions from landfills for 1 ton of MSW for fair comparison (Yadav and Samadder 2018);.....	11
Table 5. Literature review related to different leather wastes and related LCA studies.....	13
Table 6. Overview of different scenarios for utilizing waste and calculating the total carbon footprint.....	23
Table 7. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S1- RT-AD).....	30
Table 8. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S2-RT-OD).....	31
Table 9. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S3- RT-GP).....	31
Table 10. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S4-FL-AD).....	39
Table 11. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S5-FL-AD+Pyro).....	40
Table 12. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S6-FL-CO).....	40
Table 13. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S7-FL-OD).....	40
Table 14. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S8-FL-Pyro).....	40
Table 15. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S9-FL-BD).....	40
Table 16. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S10-HW-CO+SP).....	44
Table 17. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S11-HW-OD).....	44
Table 18. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S12-HW-CO+KP).....	44
Table 19. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S13-CS-AD).....	52
Table 20. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S14-CS-AD+Pyro).....	52

Table 21. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S14-CS-OD).....	52
Table 22. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S16-CS-Pyro).....	52
Table 23. : Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S17-CS-LS).....	52
Table 24. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S18-CS-INCI).....	52
Table 25. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S19-BD-OD).....	55
Table 26. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S20 &S21).....	55
Table 27. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S22-CT-OD).....	55
Table 28. The global impact from each scenario with their perspective treatment in terms of CFs followed by energy and mass recoveries.....	56
Table 29. Status of the scenarios performed for raw trimmings.....	63
Table 30. Status of the scenarios performed for fleshings.....	64
Table 31. Status of the scenarios performed for hair waste.....	64
Table 32. Status of the scenarios performed for chrome shavings.....	65
Table 33 Status of the scenarios performed for buffing dust.....	65
Table 34. Status of the scenarios performed for crust trimmings.....	66
Table 35. Status of the scenarios performed for finished trimmings.....	66
Table 36. Total carbon footprint for different auxiliary materials.....	74
Table 37. Calculation of carbon content in different leather waste.....	75
Table 38. The carbon footprint values (Buljan 2017).....	76
Table 39. Inventories data.....	78

Foreword

I want to express my sincere appreciation to everyone who supported and contributed to this research. Special thanks to PD Dr. Ing. Habil. Dirk Weichgrebe of Leibniz University Hannover for his supervision support. I want to thank Dr. Mozhiarasi Velusamy for providing hands-on mentoring throughout my thesis and assisting with data collection and validation. I appreciate the suggestions and discussion with Nhyiraba and Ammar Farooq. I appreciate my family for being with me for the whole time. It has been a long journey, but it has been amazing. I am excited to utilize the skills I have learned from my thesis.

Abstract

This comprehensive master's thesis is a significant contribution, covering the life cycle assessment (LCA) and suitable waste handling solutions for tannery waste. Input data from literature, research journals, and annual reports have been thoroughly considered, instilling confidence in the depth of this research. For analyzing the models for each leather waste, Umberto was employed for each treatment, such as anaerobic digestion, composting, open dumping, incineration, and pyrolysis. Various techniques for recovering products like gelatin, keratin, biodiesel, leather board, and sheets were also utilized.

A system boundary of "gate to gate" was applied following the standard LCA framework. Results from each treatment of leather waste are presented in terms of total carbon footprint (TCF), focusing on the impact of climate change. High emissions primarily stem from energy consumption during the treatment of leather waste. The final results are compared with scenarios involving carbon offset (Energy balance), open landfill, and carbon footprint data (sanitary landfill) provided by UNIDO. Minimal emissions from transporting 1 ton of leather waste to a treatment facility were considered for each scenario in our study. Energy and product recovery comparisons are based on quantity and market values.

The thesis concludes with a discussion of its objectives and outlines various avenues for future research, including constraints on improving the current study's carbon footprint (CF).

List of Abbreviations

- LCA: Life Cycle Assessment
- UNIDO: United Nations Industrial Development Organization
- IPCC: Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
- GHGs: Greenhouse Gases
- CO₂-eq.: Carbon Dioxide Equivalent
- LSWT: Leather Solid Waste Techniques
- LSWs: Leather Solid Waste
- PPM: Parts Per Million
- DOC: Degradable Organic Carbon
- DOC_r: Fraction of DOC Decomposing Under Anaerobic Conditions (0.0–1.0)
- OX: Oxidation Factor in Year T (Fraction)
- F: Fraction of CH₄ by Volume in Generated Landfill Gas (0.0–1.0)
- CF: Carbon Footprint
- CHP: Combined Heat and Power
- EPFR: European Pollutant Emission Register

1. Introduction

The increased demand for leather products has led to a dramatic environmental burden. This demand results in 200 times more waste than the total output from salted hides (Chojnacka et al. 2021). The leather industry is not just a pillar for economic growth for a country; it comes with challenges like production challenges and waste disposition from tanneries. Approximately 25% of the material results in products, while the remaining 75% becomes waste from every ton of salted hides. The leather waste is one of the biggest challenge to handle solid waste (Flores Tapia and Brito Moina 2023). More than half of the global leather waste originates from developing countries (UNIDO 2010). This tannery waste contains different pollutants and greenhouse gases, which are recorded from other countries such as India (Gupta and Sinha 2006).

The waste of tanneries creates an environmental burden by emitting potential greenhouse gases (GHG) into the atmosphere and pollutants into water and soil. The total emissions can be derived in the form of total CO₂-eq. The carbon footprint refers to the overall GHG released during the life cycle of a specific product, process, or service. It is typically measured in kilograms of CO₂ per unit of leather waste. According to (Watch 2022), industrial emissions have been estimated at 4.5 gigatons of CO₂ equivalent, accounting for 24% of total net greenhouse gas emissions, solely attributed to human activities (IPCC 2014).

There is a need to transition from the current linear fashion production model to a circular flow that can help reduce environmental burdens (Peters et al. 2021). There is a wide-ranging debate on climate change, the greenhouse effect, carbon footprint, environmental footprint, neutrality, sustainability, and other related issues in international climate-related organizations like UNIDO and IPCC. There are two categories of policy instruments responsible for global climate change: domestic policy instruments and international or global instruments to combat climate change (Stavins 1997). The waste generated by tanneries is on the brink of transitioning to sustainable practices due to growing environmental awareness. These linear manufacturing practices contribute to waste generation without considering alternative utilization methods. Adopting circular economy practices, such as implementing the 6R principles (Reduction, Reuse, Recycling, Recovery, Redesign, and Remanufacture), can help reduce pollution emissions and minimize waste production (Moktadir et al. 2020).

India is one of the leading countries in producing high-quality leather and waste that isn't fully utilized intensely. These wastes are rich in proteins and lipids, which can benefit biofuel production or products such as keratin, gelatin, leather boards, leather, gelatin, and biodiesel. The availability of waste, such as raw trimmings, fleshings, chrome shavings, buffing dust, and crust trimmings, generates 365.71 tons per day in India (Mozhiarasi et al. 2023). Asia is the most significant contributor to generating waste, followed by Western

Europe in Figure 1 (POPIȚA et al. 2020) . Approximately 600 metric tons of waste are generated each year globally, some of which are handled unscientific or low-costly (Fela et al. 2011; Onyuka 2010; Mozhiarasi et al. 2023) .

Figure 1. Overview of waste generated by tanneries around the world, and the graph is obtained from POPIȚA et al. (2020)

Daily, there is a total of 150 metric tons of leather waste generated, with 87 metric tons related to pre-tanning waste or beam house operations and the remaining for tanning or post-tanning operations in a tannery operation; it is estimated that from 1 ton of hide/skins, 30 m³ of water and 750-800 kg of waste is generated. About 200 to 250 kg of high-quality leather can be recovered from 1 ton of leather waste, while the remaining waste, 750 to 800 kg, can go to a treatment facility. The quality of leather produced and the level of environmental pollution can vary, depending on the type of treatment adopted and location. Globally, renewable energy reaches up to 33% of primary energy consumption, stating waste and climate change crises. Developing countries focus on biomass and promising fossil fuels, such as biogas, from different organic waste, such as tannery waste. This sustainable approach can fight climate change and provide a suitable energy source. India's population has crossed 1.428 billion and rises 1.58% daily, requiring an optimal or alternative energy source. Biogas and biofuels can be used as fuel to create energy and in diesel engines to replace diesel engines (Rajmohan et al. 2021) . Based on the origin and nature of the solid waste (leather waste), It may consist of biodegradable organic matter, which can produce compost and nutrients (Garg et al. 2024) . The most significant source of energy in India is still based on coal, which contributes 49.30% in Figure 2 (CEA 2023) ; meanwhile, the source of energy from waste treatments contributes at least 0.10% of total energy generation in India (Pwc India, 2023) .

Figure 2. Current scenario of energy production in India (CEA 2023)

Creating energy and heat via incineration and pyrolysis from chrome shavings and finishing waste (Velusamy et al. 2020), gelatin from raw trimmings (Shakil et al. 2019; Chojnacka et al. 2021), compost from fleshings (Hashem et al. 2024b), Biofuels from fleshings (Amdouni et al. 2021a), Compost from hair waste (Barrena et al. 2007b), keratin from hair waste (Ramya et al. 2022), biogas from fleshings, raw trimming and chrome shavings (Mozhiarasi et al. 2023), leather board from buffing dust (Senthil et al. 2015), and many more as mentioned in literature section, can be achieved.

This thesis analyzes the life cycle assessment (LCA) of various leather wastes using solid waste treatments (SWT) to calculate responsible CFs. It also seeks to provide a comparative analysis to determine the best utilization options for decision-makers in the leather industry for various wastes, as mentioned in Table 2. The objectives of this study, along with the thesis attached at the beginning of the report, are outlined for better understanding. This paper has been divided into sections: section 2, literature research for better experience, to align the scope of this study with the help of previous work while performing LCA. Section 3 includes the type of methodology and runs the model's most feasible data, followed by model development and the type of possible combination for scenarios. Section 4 Includes the outcomes from each potential scenario. This section compares the most sustainable techniques for individual waste with their final CF. This section also summarizes the entire paper based on the visual turn of the results from the previous section. This section also includes the limitations to improve the scope of the study and future possibilities of applying LCA analysis for further leather wastes. Section 5 summarizes the study's goal with the completion of this study with impactful results. The appendix contains detailed calculations with equations followed by the required inventories. The inventories were prepared in Excel and applied to each scenario's Umberto tool (<https://www.ifu.com/umberto/>).

2. Literature Review & LCA

Hides/skins are a by-product of slaughterhouse waste, later converted into leather. The waste produced while obtaining high-quality leather is often overlooked in linear manufacturing systems but not closed-loop ones. In this section, we have only used literature that discusses repurposing inventory data for LCA modeling.

2.1 Leather wastes and their physicochemical parameters from tanneries

The waste generated from the tannery can be categorized into three main groups: pretanning waste, tanning waste, and post-tanning waste. In the tannery process, hides or skins undergo a series of operations, each producing specific waste that will be the focus of our study. As shown in Table 1, the authors have outlined the varying quantities of waste from various tannery operations in processing 1 ton of hides and skins. The characteristics of this leather waste depend on the material's quality and the tanning processes used on the hides and skins.

Table 1. Total amount of leather waste from tanneries

Phase of tanning	Type of waste	Püntener (2007)*	Alexander (2007)*	Buljan (2000, 2007)*	Mozhiarasi (2023)*		
Unit	(kg/ton)		(kg/ton of hide/skin)		Waste (%) per ton of hides/skin	Daily waste generation in India (tons/day)	
Untanned waste	Pre-tanning waste	530	120	100	270	27	208.8
	trimmings	135	70-230	300	50	5	37.4
	Shavings	145	100	99	95	9.5	70.7
	Split	na	115	107	65	6.5	48.5
Tanned waste	Buffing dust	na	na	na	6	0.6	4.5
	Wet blue trimmings	na	na	na	30	3	22.2
	Crust trimmings	na	na	na	35	3.5	26.3
Dyed and finished waste	Shavings	10	32	10	na	-	na
	Fluff	na	2	1	na	-	na
	Total	870	439-599	637	551	55.1	418.4

* (Ozgunay et al. 2007; Mozhiarasi et al. 2023; Buljan et al. 2000; Buljan 2017)

As shown in Table 1, different authors provided the different compositions of leather waste in 1 ton of hide. Properties or physicochemical parameters of untreated waste can have a higher moisture content of up to 87%, except hair at 13.7%. Mineral substances can range

from 2-6% because there is no tanning operation, resulting in zero chrome content (Table 2). These waste materials can be used with the help of Solid waste techniques to create new products such as gelatin, biodiesel, keratin, compost, leather board and sheet, biogas, biochar, and fertilizer.

A. Raw trimmings

B. Hair waste

C. Fleshings

D. Chrome shavings

E. Buffing dust

F. Crust trimmings

G. Finishing waste

Figure 3. Different types of leather waste (A – G) as shown above on-site visit at Superhouse tannery in Kanpur and Heller leder in Hameln in Lower Saxony

Table 2. Physicochemical parameters for incoming waste for different waste

Parameters	Raw trimmings	Fleshings	Hair	Shavings/splits	Buffing dust	Crust trimmings	Finishing waste*
pH	na	11 to 13	7.9	4-6.1	524.4-5.2	5.8	5.8
Moisture (%)	60-65	75-87	11–13.7	17-19.7	10.0-15.0	13	13
Volatile solids DM* *(%)	55-63	75-82	90–91	71.3–88.8	67.7	74.8	74.76
Protein content (%)	21.5-26	5-7.2	72.8–75.0	61.6-63.9	54.5-57.5	na	na
Fat content (%)	4.25	7 to 18	2	2-5.0	1-4.5	4.2-6.9	4.2-6.9
Ash content (%)	na	6.1-8	10	10.5-15.0	10-12.8	7.9-8.1	7.9-8.1
Total chromium (%)	na	na	na	1.6-3.2	2.8-4.7	3.1	3.1
Carbon (%)	na	38.8 - 40.9 (40)	50–53.9	43	42.8-46.1 (45)	67.1	67.1
Oxygen (%)	na	36.7-41	22–26	41.3	38	7.24	7.24
Nitrogen (%)	28.7	11.3-11.6	16–18.3	8.4	7.0-10.3	9.76	9.76
Hydrogen (%)	na	8.3	7	5.8	6.1	12.6	12.6
Sulphur (%)	na	.6 -2.5	0.1–5	1.5	2.1	3.3	3.34
	(Masilamani et al. 2016)	(Kubendran et al. 2017; Ravindranath et al. 2010) ,	(Agustini et al. 2018; Da Souza et al. 2022b) ,	(Velusamy et al. 2020; Gomes et al. 2019)	(Yilmaz et al. 2007a)	(Velusamy et al. 2020)	Considered the same as crust trimmings

Here, *Assuming the same data as crust trimmings, **DM dry matter, no data

The variations in moisture content and total solids have been shown in Table 2. Fleshings contains up to 80 %. Meanwhile, buffing dust contains the least moisture. When discussing the characteristics of tanned leather, it is essential to note that tanned leather has different attributes than untanned leather.

Figure 4. Comparative view of different parameters for different leather waste (mean), followed by Table 2

For instance, untanned leather can contain around 3-6% tannins, 3-6% fat, and a 3.5-4.5% chromium content, as shown in Table 2. This results in a higher level of chromium in the effluent, including Cr^{3+} at 2.5% with 30% organic residues. The chromium levels can be as high as 500mg/kg, which is five times the acceptable level for solids (Moktadir et al. 2020; Moktadir and Rahman 2022; Mozhiarasi et al. 2023; Velusamy et al. 2020).

2.2 Possible treatments of leather wastes

2.2.1 Biological Processes - Anaerobic digestion (AD process)

Anaerobic digestion is a complex process with different stages, such as hydrolysis, fermentation, acidification, acetogenesis, and methanogenesis. In the first stage, hydrolytic bacteria break down the proteins, sugar, and fatty acids. Intermediary products like propionate and butyrate are found through acidification and acetogenesis. The last stage in the AD process, known as methanogenesis, is a natural process that converts organic waste into a new form without oxygen. This biological process generates biogas and is a sustainable energy source while reducing greenhouse gas emissions. It occurs in a sealed reactor, reducing solid waste and disposal costs. Additionally, it allows for the extraction of valuable CH_4 gas. Despite its benefits, the process only produces heat independently and requires a substantial initial investment. The anaerobic digestion process involves four simultaneous steps, as mentioned in Figure 5. Many researchers have explored various methods for handling diverse leather waste, utilizing anaerobic digestion processes to extract by-products like biogas, biochar, and bio-oil. Two digestion systems are commonly practiced: anaerobic digestion and co-digestion (Feng et al. 2019).

The raw materials may include pre-tanning waste or post-tanning waste. Most of the experiments are conducted on a small or pilot scale, where different combinations of waste are utilized to produce a substantial amount of biogas.

Figure 5. Stages of anaerobic digestion (Grippi et al. 2020)

The skin and fatty tissue of animals, known as fleshings, contain a high-fat percentage, usually between 7 and 18% (Table 2). Some writers have found that fleshings can generate significant biogas. This fat-rich waste, fleshings, can be utilized in primary and secondary sludge with a maximum biogas yield of 0.379–0.448 m³kg⁻¹.VS (Sri Bala Kameswari et al. 2011). To produce biogas, waste can be treated beforehand or used directly in anaerobic digestion. The amount of biogas produced can vary from 0.54 to 1.35 m³kg⁻¹.VS of volatile solids, depending on the waste type (Alvarez and Liden 2008).

Leather chromed waste can generate 4.1–11.3 mL-CH₄/g-VSS (Gomes et al. 2020). Keeping the chromium content low in sludge and shavings for biogas production is essential. Studies have shown that biogas production with Cr can be more than three times higher than pretanning waste, with an average of 55% CH₄ content. Maintaining high retention for up to 150 days is necessary, five times longer than pre-tanning waste. The longer retention time is due to chrome shavings with high stability, resulting from the three-dimensional collagen structure and chemical cross-links with Cr³⁺ salts formed during tanning. This stability makes them resistant to temperatures up to 110 °C and enzymatic degradation, preventing their industrial use for biogas production, which would require additional pre-treatment (shredding) and increased energy consumption from data collection (inventories), as shown in the Appendix.

Therefore, the total energy consumption for producing gas from tanning waste is higher than pre-tanning waste (Agustini et al. 2018).

2.2.2 Biological Processes - Composting

Composting has been a common practice for centuries, mainly since ancient times when manure waste was used for agriculture. Composting involves exposing organic materials to biological decomposition and stabilization at high temperatures, generating heat as a natural by-product without harming the environment (Vigneswaran et al. 2016) .

Aerobic composting involves the breakdown of organic waste with the help of oxygen, leading to the creation of CO₂, water, ammonia, and heat (Figure 1). To make sure this process goes smoothly, the waste needs to have the correct moisture content (usually 60-70%), stability, nutrient levels, particle size, pathogen levels, and a balanced C/N ratio (around 30:1) (Gonawala and Jardosh 2018) .

Figure 6. The general process of composting (aerobic) (Yap and Hadibarata 2022)

Various authors use composting to pre-treated waste with a high carbon and nitrogen content, such as fleshings, which contain up to 41% carbon and 11.6% nitrogen (Dry basis). However, in the case of hair, the C/N ratio would be higher, with carbon at 53.9% and nitrogen at 18.3% (Table 2). Both contents are perfect for producing valuable compost using various composting methods. Organic waste from multiple industries can be used as a renewable energy source. Composting and solid-state fermentation are typical methods to decrease the volume of residues and turn them into valuable by-products (Catalán et al. 2017a) . Hair waste is used in composting, and Solid state fermentation generates fertilizer. Alkaline protease can also be used for dehairing (Yazid et al. 2016) . A study was done by (Colón et al. 2012) , and different types of composting techniques were utilized with an LCA study for MSW.

2.2.3 Thermal Treatment - Pyrolysis

Pyrolysis is a process where organic waste, including leather waste, is thermally decomposed without oxygen to produce bio-fuel as a renewable alternative to fossil fuels. There are three main types of pyrolysis: slow, fast, and flash. Fast pyrolysis is the most popular due to its high heat transfer and rapid cooling of vapors, resulting in high bio-oil yield and precise temperature control. On the other hand, flash pyrolysis has poor thermal stability and can be corrosive to the solids, producing pyrolytic water (Jahirul et al. 2012; Zaman et al. 2017) .

Table 3. Overview of different types of pyrolysis processes for MSW (Varies with utilization of tannery waste) (Jahirul et al. 2012) .

Pyrolysis	Particle		Product oil (%)	Yield char(%)	Gas (%)
	Size (mm)	Temp. (K)			
Slow	5-50	550-950	30	35	35
Fast	<1	850-1250	50	20	30
Flash	<0.2	1050-1300	75	12	13

Many authors have explored various types of leather waste and attempted to determine how landfills can be avoided by implementing pyrolysis processes. They have also proposed innovative solutions for tanners and ways to increase industries' capital. The use of fleshings as pre-tanning waste has been considered, with some authors suggesting that the bio-oil yield could reach up to 60%, followed by 37.7% for biochar. Additionally, they have found that bio-oil with promising fuel properties can be obtained (Amdouni et al. 2021b) .

The main objective is to assess the total emissions that may occur while using leather waste and identify any by-products that may result. It is crucial to evaluate the energy and material consumption rates, as well as determine the most sustainable disposal method for waste to achieve a comprehensive environmental assessment (Amdouni et al. 2021b; Jahirul et al. 2012; Velusamy et al. 2020; Kluska et al. 2019) . A study on various types of leather waste for pyrolysis found that the maximum oil yield can reach up to 23%, while solid residue can go up to 48.5% at temperatures between 450-600°C (Yılmaz et al. 2007b) . Authors have observed different compositions of byproducts due to variations in reactor type and material characteristics (Yılmaz et al. 2007b) .

Some authors also utilized tanning and post-tanning waste, such as chrome shavings and finished trimming, through processes like pyrolysis and incineration, producing bio-oil at 52% and biochar at 27-30%. The experiment also demonstrated a significant weight reduction of up to 93% through incineration (Velusamy et al. 2020) . The research was based on available data (adapted as 1 ton of leather waste in case of missing data for specific waste), analyzing the input materials and energy used, as well as the emissions produced during the pyrolysis process through fluidized bed reactor (Wang et al. 2015a; Wang et al. 2021) . This reactor provides uniform heating, efficient mixing, and high heat transfer rates, which enhance the pyrolysis process's efficiency and yield the desired product

2.2.4 Thermal Treatment - Incineration

Incineration can be a better option for mitigating leather waste with a significant weight reduction. The heat generated from this process can be utilized as new energy resources, while the remaining ash can be used for further processes. However, the flue gases require

conventional air pollution control measures, as the chrome within can leach into the groundwater through ash deposition. Alternatively, the chrome can be extracted and used as raw materials for other industries. Incineration is more effective due to its proper heat recovery system, off-gas treatment, and residual ash management (Velusamy et al. 2020) . Achieving an efficient CF through incineration with energy recovery is achievable, which can help lessen the dependency on fossil fuels. The UK's municipal solid waste (MSW) CF was measured at 487 kg-CO₂eq./per ton of MSW. The CF can be further reduced by improving waste composition and energy recovery rates and utilizing alternative sources of displaced energy. This showcases that incineration can be a viable option for reducing carbon emissions (Jeswani et al. 2013) . The information needed for our current study can be obtained from similar literature sources, such as 1 ton of leather waste. This data helps determine waste treatment, ensuring no chromium content in the end product. However, if the chromium content is present and utilized correctly in the case of tanning waste, then it is possible to use this method. It is also beneficial to determine the total carbon footprint during the process with the assistance of various components of flue gases (varies with the type of waste) (Jeswani et al. 2013; Bianco et al. 2021b; Liu et al. 2017; Bisinella et al. 2021) .

2.2.5 Open dumping

Landfills have been considered the most significant source of CH₄ emissions globally after the energy and agriculture sectors. Greenhouse gas emissions from this waste sector mainly contain CO₂, CH₄, and nitrous oxide (Table 4).

Table 4. Emissions from landfills for 1 ton of MSW for fair comparison (Yadav and Samadder 2018) ;

S No.	Name of the Pollutant	Quantity of Emission (kg/t)
1	CH ₄	60
2	CO ₂	25
3	CO	0.003
4	HC	0.388
5	NO _x	0.00147
6	PM _{2.5}	0.000233

CH₄ accounts for 14% of greenhouse gas emissions in India. On a 100-year time horizon, CH₄ has a 25 times higher global warming potential, but on a 20-year time frame, CH₄ has 72 times higher global warming potential than CO₂ (CSE 2023) . When dealing with leather waste, it is impractical to dispose of it in a landfill because of its high chromium and protein content. Instead, this waste can be effectively used through different techniques for new by-products (Parvin et al. 2017) . Emissions from tannery waste depend upon the organic decomposable carbon content in specific waste; an EPFR model has been utilized to calculate total emissions in CH₄ (Menikpura and Premakumara 2021; Scharff and Jacobs 2006) . The data for the biodegradability of leather waste has been considered IPCC

(MSW) norms for MSW directly, as leather waste has unique characteristics (Change 2006; Forster et al. 2024) .

In our investigation, we can construct a reference point by comparing the acquired values from open dumping with biodegradability criteria from garden waste for pre-tanning waste and industrial waste for post-tanning waste, using UNIDO data.

2.3 Literature review based upon LCA on leather waste

The recent LCA and non-LCA studies follow this section in Table 5. More literature is needed on conducting an LCA study on leather waste. So, the data for the inventory section for energy consumption has been taken from different scientific journals with/without solid waste consideration to conduct an LCA study on each waste. The same data has been utilized in Modeling on Umberto to check the environmental burden caused by different types of leather waste.

Obtaining a bio-based fuel like biogas can play a significant role in driving towards a more sustainable green transition. Biogas typically contains 50-75% (CH₄), 30-50% CO₂, approximately 6% water vapor (H₂O), 0-1% oxygen (O₂), 0-3% nitrogen (N₂), 72-144 ppm ammonia (NH₃), 72-7200 ppm hydrogen sulfide (H₂S), and various other impurities (Yentekakis and Goula 2017) . In our situation, we generate biogas from pre-tanned and tanning waste. Extracting fleshings from pre-tanning waste can yield over 60% efficiency using various pretreatments (Kubendran et al. 2017) . Grinding may be a suitable pretreatment method for handling pre-tanning waste. Still, energy consumption could be higher for chrome-based waste when employing hydrothermal treatment, as shown in all pre-treatment data (Moktadir and Rahman 2022) . The current study uses shredding for the required scenario due to its efficiency and lower energy consumption.

After utilizing leather waste, it is possible to obtain biochar through pyrolysis. However, in the case of a controlled environment, chromium in tanned leather waste may not oxidize to hexavalent chromium ions, which is confirmed with FT-IR analysis (Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy). By pretreating the waste, biochar can be produced without any hindrance. Studies have shown that it is achievable to yield up to 52% oil and 27% biochar with the pyrolysis process. Therefore, this treatment method suits pre-tanned and tanned waste (Velusamy et al. 2020) . The parameters related to data collection are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Literature review related to different leather wastes and related LCA studies

S. No.	Waste type	Scenarios	Goal	LCA	FU, Software & method	Performed LCA	Adopted parameters from the literature	Remarks on data collection (current study)	References
1 Raw trimmings									
I		AD ^a	Utilization of raw trimmings for biogas	X	na	✓	This study obtained the average biogas potential of raw 0.547 m ³ /kg-VS. The data have been considered for the current study.	Supports data collection for AD scenario for raw trimmings	(Kubendran et al. 2017)
II		OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based on the organic decomposable carbon in waste.	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
III		RECY ^r	Utilization of raw trimmings for non-edible gelatin production	X	na	✓	extraction process at 75-85°C for 12 hours yielded non-edible gelatin.	Supports sustainability by reducing waste and potentially lowering disposal costs	(Shakil et al. 2019)
IV		RECY ^r	Collagen and gelatin production	X	na	X	Extraction of valuable products such as collagen, gelatin	Highlight of circular economy framework	(Chojnacka et al. 2021)
2 Fleshings									
I		AD ^a	Utilization of raw trimmings for biogas	X	na	✓	Average biogas potential of raw 0.455 m ³ /kg-VS The data have been considered for the current study.	Supports data collection for AD scenario for raw trimmings	(Kubendran et al. 2017; Ravindranath et al. 2010)
II		CO ^e	Co-composting with chicken excreta, sawdust, and cow pats	X	na	✓	Final compost with a high yield of 76.63%	In inventory as input and output	(Hashem et al. 2024)
III		OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
IV		Pyro ^p	Waste into high-value biofuels and biochars at 600°C	X	na	✓	60 wt% (bio-oil) at optimal pyrolysis conditions (600°C), at 600°C it was about 27 wt% (biochar), remaining will be syngas	Lacking in emission data, Adopting input and output data	(Amdouni et al. 2021)
V		INCI ⁱ	Incineration of fleshings in a tunnel furnace system to	X	1 ton	X	Combustion Residue – Ash (4.6% w/w) is the only data helpful for inventory.	Only paper available with no emission data	(Famielec and Wieczorek-Ciurowa

		manage waste and recover energy.						2013)
VI	INCI ⁱ	Waste to energy (MSW)	✓	1 kWh, SimaPro	X	Production of energy of 711.94 kWh	CF for incineration is 0.841 kg CO ₂ -eq./kWh; CF may vary with methods and boundaries.	(Bianco et al. 2021)
VII	RECY ^r	CF of biodiesel production	✓	na	X	No information is available for CF.	Information not available	(Kiliç et al. 2014)
VIII	RECY ^r	Biodiesel production	X	na	✓	Obtaining oil of 26.32 g from using NH ₄ Cl at 200 g of flesh with a particle with an average of 12.5% fat content	No LCA was performed.	(Sandhya et al. 2016)
IX	RECY ^r	Biodiesel production from different free fatty acid-rich wastes.	✓	1 ton of biodiesel produced, SimaPro	✓	CF (GWP) of Beef tallow: 72.94 kg CO ₂ eq./ton was obtained	Data for energy consumption in esterification and transesterification has been utilized, which is useful for the inventory section.	(Dufour and Iribarren 2012)

3 Hair waste

I	SSF and CO ^o	Traditional composting using turned windrow or in-vessel systems for solid-state fermentation to produce proteases and compost as a secondary product.	✓	100 kg of hair waste, Sima Pro 8	X	Low energy consumption and high environmental burden because of emissions, Comparison of GWP of CO and SSF (20% lower).	Utilizing inventory data from Colón, Cadena et al. 2012	(Catalán et al. 2017)
II	MSW (CO ^o)	Utilizing organic fractions (MSW) through In-vessel composting (Current scenario)	✓	1 ton of OFMSW, No info for software	X	Different values for different scenarios of composting, such as CT (Composting in Vessel), CCW (Composting in Confined Windrows), ADC (Anaerobic Digestion Plus Composting), TW (Turned Windrow Composting), HC (Home Composting), followed by GWP and other categories	Utilizing the inventory section for hair waste with CF (150 kg CO ₂ -eq/FU for in-vessel composting) and with CF (190 kg CO ₂ -eq/FU . Turned windrow composting) followed by CF for other scenarios.	(Colón et al. 2012)
III	MSW (CO ^o)	Literature review for Green MSW with different sources	✓	FU varies, Simapro	X	Overview of different environmental burdens with various technology and operational settings.	Need for standardized approaches in data collection and defining system boundaries.	(Oviedo-Ocaña et al. 2023)

					mostly.			
IV	Hair waste (CO ^o)	Co-composting with hair waste and sewage sludge (1:1)	X	na	✓	Final standard compost with 57.8% from hair waste and sewage sludge	There is no information for LCA analysis, but data collection for the inventory section	(Barrena et al. 2007)
V	LF ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste	Supports data collection for Open and sanitary landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
VI	OD ⁱ	Examining the presence of hair waste with other leather wastes	X	na	X	Hair waste does not impact the AD process, with a maximum daily output of 19.4 ml/g of VSS.	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Agustini et al. 2018)
VII	RECY ^r	Extraction of keratin with the help of different chemical treatments	X	na	✓	Output as a powder (40 gm/l, Da Souza, Benvenuti, et al. 2022)	No LCA was performed, and insufficient data for data collection	(Ramya et al. 2022)

4 Chrome shavings & Splits

I	AD ^a	Utilization of raw trimmings for biogas	X	na	✓	Average biogas potential of raw 0.455 m ³ /kg-VS	Supports data collection for AD scenario for raw trimmings	(Gomes et al. 2019)
II	OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
III	Pyro ^p	Utilization of finished trimmings (LFT) and chrome shavings (CS).	X	na	✓	Bio-oil 52% (LFT) and 49%(CS); Biochar 27% (LFT) and 30% (CS); pyrolysis gases 21% (LFT) and 21% (CS) are obtained as a result.	Only output data have been taken for the inventory section; no LCA study was found.	(Velusamy et al. 2020)
	INCI ⁱ		X	na	✓	Both LFT and CS showed high weight reduction (over 93%)	However, an LCA study is performed in the current study.	
IV	RECY	utilization of chrome shavings as leather sheet	X	na	✓	A leather sheet was manufactured by intermixing natural rubber (latex), papermill sludge, and ethylene glycol.	No LCA was found, but data was collected for the inventory section of the current study (Current scenario). However, a LCA study is performed.	(Senthil et al. 2023)

5 Buffing dust

I	OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
---	-----------------	-----------------------	---	----	---	---	--	---------------------------

II	Pyro ^p	Pyrolysis of buffing dust at 450°C and 600°C	X	na	✓	Result as gas (16.8% to 20.0%) and oil (22.2% to 23.5%), with decreases in char (40.1% to 37.5%) and ammonium carbonate (6.2% to 3.9%) as the temperature rose.	No LCA study was found; However, a LCA study is performed.	(Onur Yılmaz et al. 2007)
III	CO ^c	The waste has been used with Cow dung and chicken manure with C: N as 25-30:1.	X	na	X	N, P, K, and S values up to standard; pH for microbial activity and plant growth (6.0-8.5).	No LCA study was found; No data is available for further modeling.	(Belal Hossain, Md Abul Hashem et al. 2023)

6 Crust trimmings & Splits

I	OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste.	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
---	-----------------	-----------------------	---	----	---	--	--	---------------------------

7 Leather finished trimmings (LFT)

I	OD ⁱ	Calculating emissions	X	na	✓	Methane percentage is based upon the organic decomposable carbon in waste	Supports data collection for Open landfill	(Scharff and Jacobs 2006)
II	Pyro ^p	Utilization of Leather finished trimmings (LFT) and chrome shavings (CS).	X	na	✓	Same data as mentioned in chrome shavings section	Only output data have been taken for the inventory section; no LCA study was found. However, an LCA study is performed.	(Velusamy et al. 2020)
	INCI ⁱ		X	na	✓	Same data as mentioned in chrome shavings section		

Here,

a: AD Anaerobic digestion,

r : RECY Recycling

c: CO Composting

l: OD Open dumping

p: PYR Pyrolysis

i: INCI Incineratio

As shown in Table 5, the data was collected to perform different possible scenarios through the LCA methodology. This table also indicates our study's existing LCA studies and scenarios (model development).

As tannery waste has a high organic content, it is also an excellent option to convert it into organic fertilizer with the help of different composting techniques and required pretreatment. Regarding fleshings or trimmings, it is possible to utilize the waste directly through pretreatment, such as hydrothermal, chemical, hydrolysis, or shredding. Compost quality will also depend upon the required days, temperature, and quantity or type of substrate. In the case of hair, there is a need to use a substrate like dry waste sludge or anything. It is also essential to keep in mind the C/N ratio, which should be near 20:1, which can also be obtained with composting (Onyuka 2010; Catalán et al. 2017a; Abraham et al. 2014; Barrena et al. 2007a; Yazid et al. 2016) .

Our current study is still being conducted on the potential of utilizing tanning waste as compost due to a need for more information. The carbon balance has been considered to calculate total emissions in the composting scenarios for fleshings and hair waste, as shown in Table 5. These leather wastes require pretreatment, such as modified alkaline hydrolysis, which already has a high requirement of chemicals. This makes composting from tanning or post-tanning waste infeasible while considering sustainability goals. Data from the organic carbon fraction has been considered to evaluate the emission of CO₂ in the case of fleshings (Hashem et al. 2024a) . To handle hair waste, the data for input and output materials, such as compost percentage, substrate, and co-substrate, has been adopted (Barrena et al. 2007a) .

Our study focuses on sustainably using tannery waste. The quantity of hair waste generated during the tanning process can burden industries and the environment. However, this waste can be converted into valuable products through effective treatments like alkali hydrolysis (Ramya et al. 2022; Ramya et al. 2020; Da Souza et al. 2022) .

Leather waste, such as chrome shavings and buffing dust, are excellent materials that can be repurposed for other uses, such as creating a leather board or composite material. These waste materials are stabilized with chromium salts during tanning, making them suitable for recycling applications. The fibers have great strength and flexibility, allowing them to be used with water, natural rubber, ethylene glycol, and sulfuric acid to produce a leather board that can be utilized for various purposes (Senthil et al. 2023a; Senthil et al. 2015) . Production of the leather board with the help of the waste mentioned above can lead to higher consumption of natural rubber latex, resulting in a higher carbon footprint.

Raw trimmings are the best choice for making non-edible gelatin, which can be further utilized as semi-gluten. Trimmings can come from pre-tanning, post-tanning, or

finishing leather waste. The trimmings can have hair in small quantities without any problem because the sulfur dissolves the hair. However, in more significant amounts, the color of the gelatin can vary. Approximately 40 kg of raw trimmings can be obtained from 1000 kg of raw hide or skin. Gelatin, derived from collagen, can create high viscosity in hot water and can freeze at lower temperatures. This makes it ideal for gelling agents, thickeners, stabilizers, coatings, etc. Gelatin can be a mixture of peptides and proteins produced from the partial hydrolysis of collagen (Shakil et al. 2019). The maximum amount of collagen that can be extracted from trimmings is 55%, while the amount of gelatin that can be obtained from gelatin is 14.24% (Masilamani et al. 2023).

For conversation, biowaste (fleshings) can be collected from a tannery and proceed for biodiesel production. Fleshings are a suitable alternative for a high biodiesel yield because of their high fat content, 7 – 18% (Table 2), and a high free fatty acid (FFA) value of about 44%. It is a promising raw material for biodiesel production. The waste must be naturalized, requiring Hydrochloric acid (HCl) and ammonium chloride (NH₄Cl) (Sandhya et al. 2016; Sousa et al. 2017). This step can impact the efficiency of the extraction of biodiesel from fleshings. During naturalization, oil is extracted, followed by heat and energy, which is required for this step (Sousa et al. 2017). The esterification process was optimized to convert this non-edible crude grease into fatty acid methyl esters (FAME), focusing on temperature, acid concentration, oil-to-methanol molar ratio, and reaction time. Oils with FFA content above 2% require acid pretreatment before transesterification to avoid soap formation. Solid waste can be utilized as helpful compost because there is no chromium content. The fat contains high free fatty acids (FFAs), followed by heat treatment and acid catalysis with H₂SO₄ and methanol (Kubendran et al. 2017; Saranya and Ramachandra 2020; Dufour and Iribarren 2012). The sulfuric acid concentration is critical in esterification. Stepwise conversion involves triglycerides to diglycerides, diglycerides to monoglycerides, and monoglycerides to glycerol. The transesterification rate increases at 75°C. The pretreated oil is then subjected to transesterification followed by methanol, and an alkaline catalyst and heat treatment are used (Dufour and Iribarren 2012; Sousa et al. 2017). Later, the biodiesel can be purified, followed by drying or wet washing (Alamsyah and Loebis 2014). Because of the lower fat content in other leather waste, gaining a high yield through biodiesel production is impractical and uneconomical.

3. Materials and Methods

This study determined the most suitable solid waste technologies for disposing or utilizing specific leather waste based on the total carbon footprint (CF) during the whole process after using the LCA methodology. LCA is a valuable method for analyzing all the different stages involved in creating and using a product or service.

In our study, we focused on obtaining by-products from leather waste. This technique is typically divided into four main stages: goal definition, scope, inventory analysis, and interpretation (ISO 1998; ISO 2000; ISO 2006). The primary purpose of LCA is to carefully gather and evaluate inputs and outputs to understand the environmental impacts of a product or service (Technical Committee ISO/TC 207, Environmental Management 2006). The main goal of conducting a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for utilizing tannery waste is to go beyond just energy recovery. It also includes preventing landfill disposal (White et al. 1995; McDougall et al. 2008). A visual process flowchart has been created below to illustrate the various steps and connections involved in the processes (Figure 7).

3.1 Boundary Conditions and Functional Unit

To conduct a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), it is essential to define clear boundaries to determine what should and should not be included. This challenge can be addressed through three categories: Scope 1, Scope 2, and Scope 3. Scope 1 encompasses direct emissions from various processes, while Scope 2 covers emissions related to the transportation of goods and waste disposal. Scope 3 includes emissions that are not accounted for in the first two scopes, such as the Extraction of minerals (Fantozzi and Bartocci 2016; Muthu 2014).

Figure 7. Boundary conditions for utilizing leather waste (current study)

Our study has extensively researched how the environment impacts human health, ecosystems, and global resources. The current study must focus on the entire

utilization process from 'gate to gate,' as waste from one process (tannery processes) can be used as input, creating a more sustainable approach (by-products). (Colley et al. 2020; Mezzullo et al. 2013) .

When conducting an in-depth analysis of the environmental impacts associated with different types of leather waste, a crucial tool is the reference flow or functional unit. This unit standardizes the input and output within the system, enabling a quantitative assessment of the performance of product systems. In our study, the reference flow is represented by using 1 ton of leather waste as FU from a tannery through solid waste techniques, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impact.

3.2 Inventories (data collection in Appendix)

One of the fundamental steps in our research is establishing system boundaries and conditions. This process involves identifying all inputs, outputs, and auxiliary materials used across various processes. By clearly defining these parameters, we can ensure a comprehensive and accurate assessment of the environmental impact of utilizing leather waste.

- **Raw materials (input):** The waste material generated from tanneries, such as solid leather waste, is readily available for further utilization. Different waste streams from tanneries, such as pre-tanning and chrome tanning wastes, can be effectively utilized in various waste management processes (Mozhiarasi et al. 2023; Moktadir and Rahman 2022) . These include anaerobic digestion, pyrolysis, and incineration (Velusamy et al. 2020; Moktadir and Rahman 2022) . Pre-tanning wastes are suitable for composting, while hair waste can be recycled into different products (Abraham et al. 2014; Barrena et al. 2007a; Catalán et al. 2017a; Da Souza et al. 2022a; Onyuka et al. 2012) . Buffing dust, a primary environmental concern, can be repurposed into leather board and fabric composites (Senthil et al. 2023a; Mondal et al. 2022) . This strategic utilization of tannery wastes promotes sustainable waste management and contributes to the recovery of valuable resources.
- **Energy:** The current study has considered heat, electricity, and hard coal production from the ecoinvent database. In Umberto, we have considered using electricity (from coal production) in northern India with a CF of 1.71 kg-CO₂ eq./ton of waste. A heat energy (MJ) with a CF of 0.0035 kg-CO₂eq./ton of waste has also been taken from ecoinvent. We assumed these values for energies for the whole current study.
- **Transport:** These utilization processes require transportation, which incurs fuel consumption. Data for a lorry's fuel usage for transporting 1 ton of leather waste over a distance of 20km is transported by freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric tons, sourced from the Ecoinvent database. To match the capacity of carrying leather waste, a comparable entry can be selected to keep the results constant.

- **Other inputs:** The auxiliary materials, such as chemicals, have been utilized across various utilization processes, as detailed in the Appendix, with CO₂ kg per kg of required material (Appendix)

A methodology for impact assessment is critical when measuring environmental impacts or burdens. Many researchers have opted for different methodologies easily accessible through the Umberto software. It's important to mention that there are alternative methodologies like CML 2001, TRACI, and IPCC, each with its own unique set of indicators. We decided on IPCC 2021 due to its relevance to the global warming potential we focus on and its alignment with our data collection.

Warming rates have been predicted to be 0.26 [0.2–0.4] °C per decade over 2014–2023, a leading cause of climate change (Forster et al. 2024). Tracking down the emission of leather waste while utilizing solid waste techniques, including energy and material consumption, was the biggest motivation for this study (thesis).

3.3 Different solid waste pathways (a sustainable approach)

The Umberto model may now be assessed after completing all process flow paths with inventory assistance from various literature.

Figure 8. Overview of waste treatment hierarchy in order of preference (AlQattan et al. 2018)

It is impossible to show the carbon footprint for every solid waste technique because data is only available for sanitary landfills for different leather wastes (Buljan 2017). In our case, open dumping was invested in various types of leather waste. The current

study can be the first collection of all possible waste with background literature to calculate the carbon footprint of varying leather waste using other solid waste techniques in section 2.3.

The current study used the waste hierarchy in order of activity until the end of disposal to prevent leather waste from being dumped openly. Meanwhile, the leather waste in open dumping is still practiced in some parts of the world, including India (Moktadir et al. 2020). We ran scenarios for each sort of leather waste to determine the CO₂ emissions (Figure 8).

Figure 9. The SDGs' goals relate to our current study (United Nations 2019; Oliveira et al. 2024).

There are 17 sustainable development goals, goal 12 emphasizing responsible consumption and production, and goal 13 as climate action have been adopted through innovative processes and clean energy, followed through this current study (United Nations 2019; Oliveira et al. 2024).

3.4 Model Development

LCA analysis in current research focused on tannery waste management necessitates a comprehensive data collection phase (Appendix). This should include all inputs and outputs, including materials and energy, as well as direct and indirect emissions. Early establishment of these factors is critical for a thorough inventory. The adverse impacts on the environment, followed by carbon footprint (CF), will be discussed in the next section. Following this, various scenarios can be evaluated to explore potential improvements in waste management processes. This section consists only of scenarios that can be performed with data from the literature.

Model development has been followed as:

Quantities: 1 ton of leather waste (FU)

Scenarios: Anaerobic digestion (including pyrolysis), Anaerobic digestion, composting, landfilling, pyrolysis, incineration, leather sheet production, gelatin, keratin, and biodiesel production

Table 6. Overview of different scenarios for utilizing waste and calculating the total carbon footprint

S.No.	Type of waste	Model scenarios	Treatments
1	Raw Trimmings	S1- RT-AD	Anaerobic digestion
2		S2-RT-OD	Open dumping
3		S3-RT-GP	Gelatin production
4	Fleshings	S4-FL-AD	Anaerobic digestion
5		S5-FL-AD+Pyro	Anaerobic digestion+CHP + Pyrolysis
6		S6-FL-CO	Composting (turned windrow)
7		S7-FL- OD	Open dumping
8		S8-FL-Pyro	Pyrolysis + CHP
9		S9-FL-BF	Biodiesel production
10	Hair waste	S10-HW-CO+SP	Composting (static pile)
11		S11-HW- OD	Open dumping
12		S12-HW-KP	Keratin production
13	Chrome shavings & splits	S13-CS-AD	Anaerobic digestion
14		S14-CS-AD+Pyro	Anaerobic digestion+ CHP + Pyrolysis
15		S15-CS- OD	Open dumping
16		S16-CS-Pyro	Pyrolysis +CHP
17		S17-CS-LS	Leather sheet
18		S18-CS-INCI	Incineration
19	Buffing dust	S19-BD- OD	Open dumping
20		S20-BD-BO	Leather board
21		S21-BD-Pyro	Pyrolysis with CHP unit
22	Crust trimmings	S22-CT- OD	Open dumping
23	Finishing waste	S23-FTW-Pyro	Pyrolysis with CHP unit
24		S24-FTW-INCI	Incineration
25		S25-FTW- OD	Open dumping

The results of these scenarios will be discussed in the next section. The overview of individual or combined treatments is mentioned in Table 6.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Carbon footprint emissions of each scenario

Waste 1. Raw trimmings

S1- RT-AD: The AD process uses the first 1000 kg intake as input waste. For every travel scenario, a 20 km radius has been considered for managing 1 ton of waste leather, and Ecoinvent data has been utilized to generate an emission factor. Energy consumption for pretreatment has been adopted as 0.045 kWh/ton (Xavier et al. 2015). A conveyor belt with an energy consumption of 0.03 kWh/ton has been provided for moving the waste in the waste facility (Yao et al. 2020). The pretreatment increases the waste's surface area and makes it more accessible for microbial degradation. The data collection in the inventory section shows that the physicochemical parameters have been considered. In the digestion chamber, 0.0054 kWh/ton of waste of electricity was consumed in processing (Frost and Gilkinson 2010).

Because of the higher organic content, biogas will be 0.547 m³/kg-VS from raw trimmings (Masilamani et al. 2016). This biogas will be utilized as input post-treatment with a sand filter and hydrogen sulfide removal treatment with an energy consumption of 0.11 kWh/m³ using the compressor and 0.117 kWh/m³ with NaOH of 0.04 kg/m³, respectively (Alengebawy et al. 2022). After biogas purification, a CHP unit with an energy consumption of 0.02 kWh/m³ has been utilized (Abbasi et al. 2015). The percentages for heat and electricity were 37.3% and 51.5%. A total of 12% of the loss of biogas has also been considered. It has been established that the CHP unit receives 22 MJ/m³ of total energy, which is used to verify heat and power production (Alengebawy et al. 2022).

Conversely, a conveyor belt provides the digestate into the dewatering unit (Figure 10). An amount of energy consumption of 0.04 kWh/kg for dewatering has been considered (Mohammadi et al. 2019). The dewatering ratio, a crucial factor in the process, has been meticulously considered as the complete moisture removal. This means the remaining wet digestate will undergo further processes, such as pyrolysis (Zimmer et al. 2022), reported. The digestate can be used as a biofertilizer directly after complete dewatering because no data have been found for using raw trimming as input material for pyrolysis.

In the current scenario of the AD process (Figure 10), the amount of biogas of 121 m³ has been obtained, which can be treated and utilized further through the CHP unit. The CHP unit will produce a heat of 1371 MJ and electricity of 273 kWh, considering a 12% loss of biogas during production. After dewatering, 325 kg of digestate can be used for agricultural applications.

Figure 10. Model description for S1- RT-AD as baseline scenario

Figure 11. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S1- RT-AD

CF: For the current scenario, A total CF of 293 kg-CO₂eq./ton of raw trimmings is emitted throughout the whole AD process.

In the current scenario, the amount of energy used for pretreatment (shredding) is 45 kWh/ton of waste used and kept constant for each scenario (Xavier et al. 2015), which will be the second highest CF contributor in the AD process with 77.06 kg-CO₂eq./ton (Figure 11). Impact by transportation will be the most minor concern in current modeling because of its low CF in the current study.

By applying purification techniques, the CF for sulfur removal is 17.69 kg-CO₂eq./ton to treat 121 m³ of biogas from 1 ton of waste.

In addition, the CF for the CHP unit is found to be 100 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste from contribution analysis in the model.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste	93.459	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	81.714	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg (GLO, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg)	131.358	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	76.083	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	51.651	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	3.623	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Semidreid digestate	67.896	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	67.896	kg CO ₂ -Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 12. Contribution of all flows through S1- RT-AD with carbon footprint

The highest contribution of CF in the current scenario is from electricity consumption, followed by CF of auxiliary materials like NaOH and lubricating oil to run the CHP unit (Figure 12).

Considering carbon offset has been taken into account to check the amount of carbon that can be utilized back into the process or transferred to the grid (Arendt et al. 2021; Rinke Dias de Souza, Nariê et al. 2021; Maalouf and El-Fadel 2019).

$$\text{Carbon offset} = \text{Form of energy} * \text{Emission factor for energy} \in \text{the current study}$$

Carbon offsets are obtained through energy production that reduces emissions or improves carbon sequestration in our study. The energy produced through the system is multiplied by the emission factor in the same study to calculate carbon offsets.

After considering carbon offset, 1.71 kg-CO₂eq./kg for electricity from coal and .0035 kg-CO₂eq./kg for heat from ecoinvent has been considered for energy produced from S1- RT-AD 1371 MJ and electricity of 273 kWh. The total carbon offset of 471.6 kg-CO₂eq./ton of raw trimmings for S1- RT-AD has been obtained, which is considered a sustainable approach. This is arrived at by considering the system boundary as " gate to gate".

S2-RT-OD: Handling bio-waste can be risky if there is no optimal solution for waste disposal, in this case, landfills (Lakhout and Alsulami 2020) .

Figure 13. Model description for open dumping for raw trimmings as a baseline scenario for other leather wastes

Landfill techniques can be divided into open dumping and sanitary landfills with energy utilization. Raw trimmings can be directly disposed of in open dumping (considered in the current study). The EPER model from Germany has been considered to calculate the amount of methane emitted from open landfills, followed by the utilization of degradable carbon present in each waste (Scharff and Jacobs 2006) . The same model, with more factors for dividing categories of waste, has been provided by (Menikpura and Premakumara 2021) . A set of equations with different parameters will determine how much CH₄ will be produced per ton of waste, considering no previous dumping log. As mentioned in the inventory section (Appendix), the average amount of carbon content and total solids of all wastes have been adapted from Table 2. Considering the total amount of only degradable carbon in raw trimmings, 150 kg goes to open dumping. However, the EPFR model followed the amount of degraded carbon (Scharff and Jacobs 2006) .

CF: The total CF of 1189 kg-CO₂eq./ton of raw trimmings will be emitted from the open dumping site, which can be a potential pollutant in the greenhouse effect.

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
Fleshings		1,190.513	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Landfill		1,190.510	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Transport		0.003	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 14. Contribution of all processes through S2- RT-LF with carbon footprint

Carbon offset indicates that when raw trimmings are dumped in the open dumping, one ton of leather waste can produce methane per year using the zero-order model (Scharff and Jacobs 2006). Leachate infiltration can seriously pollute soil, surface, and groundwater in groundwater contamination. Moreover, gas emissions and underground water pollution may have adverse health effects, producing carcinogenic and non-carcinogenic effects on the nearby exposed population (Siddiqua et al. 2022).

However, (Pérez et al. 2018) stated the worst scenario with a reduced amount of 1597 kg-CO₂eq./ton of MSW waste (88%), including 10 % food and 30 % textile waste.

Considering CH₄ as a pollutant contributing to CF in open dumping in the current scenario, this scenario is not recommended for practicing further.

S3-RT-GP: Following the sustainable approach, the goal of this paper was not only to find suitable techniques to mitigate environmental burden but also to utilize waste in a suitable product. The raw trimmings can be used as a source for gelatin in Figure 15 (Shakil et al. 2019; Masilamani et al. 2023; Alipal et al. 2021; Sebastian 2014).

The study case has been assumed with an input of 1000 kg of raw trimmings (Shakil et al. 2019). The data for each auxiliary material, such as chemicals, energy, and water, have been reported in the inventories in the Appendix.

The raw trimmings will go through for washing with two times water per ton of waste. The waste, after washing, goes through the soaking stage, followed by a wetting agent, preservatives, and sodium carbonate. This mixed solution from the soaking stage passes through roasting for 30 minutes at 93 °C, and 95% of the water that has been utilized will be removed. Later, the mixed material has to go through the liming stage, mixed with sodium sulfide, lime, and HCl with a liming auxiliary. Excessive water will be removed after completion. The remaining mixed material passes through the design and is followed by ammonium sulfate and chloride. Later, this waste goes through melting and drying at 80°C and 140°C for flash heating. Following the production process of gelatin (Shakil et al. 2019), 46% of total solids Will be obtained as gelatin through different stages of production.

Figure 15. Model description for S3- RT-GP

CF: The total CF throughout the process is 342 kg-CO₂eq./ton of raw trimmings. Producing gelatin of 172 kg (46% of total solids) can be considered an excellent alternative to making a sustainable product.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather_waste	12.044	kg CO2-Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	0.298	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gelatin	330.340	kg CO2-Eq
sodium sulfite	82.034	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	81.921	kg CO2-Eq
hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state	74.083	kg CO2-Eq
sodium bicarbonate	37.343	kg CO2-Eq
ammonium sulfate	25.266	kg CO2-Eq
ammonium chloride	22.711	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	3.880	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 16. Contribution of all flows through S3- RT-GP with carbon footprint emissions

The main contribution of CF to producing gelatin from raw trimmings is energy consumption and auxiliary materials (Figure 16).

Figure 17. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S3- RT-GP

Comparing the GWP in the current scenario, liming will produce high CF, followed by the pretreatment and melting process. Considering the sustainable product recovery with economic interest, this scenario can be a good alternative for using raw trimmings as waste.

Comparison among S1- RT-AD, S2-RT-OD, and S3- RT-GP based on energy balance:

Table 7. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S1- RT-AD).

Input energy		CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	115.5	293	1371	273	471	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 8. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S2-RT-OD)

Input energy		CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	0	1189	-	-	-	Avoided

* Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 9. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S3- RT-GP)

Input energy		CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	103.9	342	-	-	Gelatin	Yes

* Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

After comparing the results from current scenarios, the AD process is recommended for energy recovery and gelatin for product recovery, according to their CFs, as shown in the comparison of all three scenarios (Table 7 and Table 9)

Waste 2: Fleshings

S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro: This section will follow only the AD+Pyrolysis process, considering all base data from S1- RT-AD. Regarding fleshing waste, the biogas yield of 0.455 m³/kg VS has been considered the base scenario (Kubendran et al. 2017) .

Before performing pyrolysis for fleshings waste, a comprehensive mass balance calculates the amount of evaporated water and the required heat. The specific heat capacity, as detailed in the Appendix, has been calculated using the equation from (Chen et al. 2014; Hossain et al. 2024) and the moisture loss with required heat from (Zimmer et al. 2022; Maurer and Müller 2019) .

Heat required (MJ/kg)= Targated waste * Specific heat capacity* Temp difference (Kelvin)

$$HR (MJ/kg)=W(kg) * SHC(KJ.kg^{-1} k^{-1}) * \Delta (^{\circ}C)$$

In the case of fleshings, the data for output products like biochar, bio-oil, and pyrolysis gas has been meticulously adapted (Amdouni et al. 2021b) . The gas utilization from the pyrolysis unit has been thoroughly discussed in a separate pyrolysis scenario. The energy consumption for the pyrolysis unit has been taken as 0.334 kWh/ton of waste (Wang et al. 2015b; Wang et al. 2021) . Other emission data have already been mentioned in the inventory section. However, 37% of biochar and 60% of bio-oil will be produced (Amdouni et al. 2021) .

Figure 18. Model description for S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro

CF: Considering only the AD process for fleshings, a total CF of 245 kg-CO₂eq./ton of fleshings will be emitted.

Meanwhile, 72 m³ of biogas is calculated from the AD process for fleshings. However, a CHP unit will produce biogas in heat of 824 MJ and electricity of 165 kWh per ton of fleshings, making it a viable source of energy recovery.

CF: S5-FL-AD+Pyro can result in a higher total CF of 283 kg-CO₂eq./ton of fleshings emitted, which can come under an energy recovery. The current scenario also indicates the most minor recovery of products.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather waste	93.486	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	81.741	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO ₂ -Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biochar for further use	72.400	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	42.450	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	17.506	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	6.988	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Methane, fossil	4.621	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.834	kg CO ₂ -Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biooil	116.869	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	68.524	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	28.259	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	11.281	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Methane, fossil	7.460	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	1.346	kg CO ₂ -Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 19. Contribution of all flows through S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro with carbon footprint emissions

Figure 20. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro

Considering the S4-FL-AD and S5-FL-AD+Pyro scenarios, the pretreatment will produce high CF, followed by a common dewatering unit in Figure 19 and Figure 20.

The total amount of energy as heat of 824 MJ and electricity of 165 kWh per ton of fleshings will be produced the same in AD and AD with pyrolysis unit (common CHP unit in both scenarios). These scenarios can be considered in energy and product recovery, followed by a sustainable approach.

S6-FL-CO: Because of the carbon to nitrogen balance, it is possible to use fleshings and hair waste as a fertilizer (compost) free from heavy metals like chromium if we can use optimal cosubstrate to balance the C: N ratio.

Figure 21. Model description for S6-FL-CO

This scenario will be folded with the same pretreatment and transportation phase as shown in scenarios for anaerobic digestion with the exact quantities of energy consumption. After applying shredding, the fleshings have to go through pre and post-mechanical treatment (trommel) with energy consumption of 1.1 & 0.8kWh/ton of waste, respectively (Komilis and Ham 2004). A study case uses different quantities of cosubstrates for fleshings in S6-FL-CO (Hashem et al. 2024b). The emissions data and the moisture balance with air supply have been considered (Boldrin et al. 2011), broadly as mentioned in inventories.

The percentages of emissions have been calculated from the carbon balance. An equation for carbon mass balance has been considered:

Total amount of carbon present in leather waste

$$= \text{Amount of waste as FU (kg)} * \text{Total solids(kg)} * \text{Carbon content (\%)}$$

Considering the total amount of fleshings for turned windrow composting with the required substrate as mentioned in the inventory section (Hashem et al. 2024b), 77% amount of compost of input material from 1000 kg of fleshings and 556 kg of co-substrates has been produced while balancing carbon content and moisture balance (Boldrin et al. 2011).

CF: Utilizing fleshings through turned windrow composting will produce a total CF of 268 kg-CO₂eq./ton of fleshings has been evaluated.

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
Cowpats		4.139	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pretreatments (Shredding)		3.253	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Manual mixing		0.886	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Chicken excreta		5.730	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pretreatments (Shredding)		4.504	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Manual mixing		1.227	kg CO ₂ -Eq
compost (GLO, market for compost)		220.591	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Turned windrow		179.792	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pretreatments (Shredding)		30.775	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Manual mixing		8.382	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Treatment through trommel		1.642	kg CO ₂ -Eq
leather waste		38.532	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pretreatments (Shredding)		38.532	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 22. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S6-FL-CO

In this scenario, most energy will be consumed during composting operations, followed by pretreatment and CO₂ from compost production (Figure 22).

S7-FL-OD: The amount of 39.9 kg of CH₄ for 1 ton of fleshings from open dumping has been calculated with the help of the EPER model as mentioned in the scenario for open dumping in raw trimmings (Scharff and Jacobs 2006; Scharff et al. 2007).

CF: The total carbon footprint emitted through the landfill will be 1189 kg-CO₂eq./ton of fleshings (Scharff and Jacobs 2006).

S8-FL-Pyro: The remaining amount will be considered pyrolysis gas with LHV of 8MJ/m³ at 600 °C (Amdouni et al. 2021b). The LHV for gas has been verified (Moghadam et al. 2014; Noushabadi et al. 2021). However, the process requires adequate up to 15% moisture content, which can be reduced through mechanical dewatering and solar drying with extra heat as a source of additional energy (Zimmer et al. 2022; Aragon-Briceño et al. 2022; Yao et al. 2020).

The inventory section mentions the emissions from the pyrolysis unit for fleshings. Gas from the pyrolysis unit can be utilized as a source of heat, which requires a compressor and burner with water as a medium (Figure 23). The data for the boiler unit is also mentioned in the inventory section. (Alengebawy et al. 2022).

Figure 23. Model description for pyrolysis (fleshings)

CF: Considering pyrolysis as a solution for fleshing wastes, a CF of 257 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input fleshings is emitted with a yield of 13% biochar and 21 % bio-oil through pyrolysis. The current scenario can be an optimal solution for product recovery.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste	50.277	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	38.532	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biochar	74.133	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	69.602	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg	4.531	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biooil	119.666	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	112.352	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg	7.314	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, low voltage (IN-Northern grid, electricity voltage transformation from medium to low voltage)	5.638	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	4.285	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	1.354	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg (GLO, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg)	7.785	kg CO ₂ -Eq
lubricating oil	5.916	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	1.869	kg CO ₂ -Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 5E9l/year	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 24. Overview of the amount of emissions emitted from entries in S8-FL-Pyro

Figure 25. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S8-FL-Pyro

The energy produced through pyrolysis with the CHP unit is minimal because of the meager amount of volatile solids and the high amount of moisture in fleshings. The main contribution of the CO₂ emitted in this scenario will come from pretreatment, followed by a pyrolysis unit and a dewatering unit (Figure 25). Most emissions will come from pretreatment and pyrolysis because of high energy consumption (Figure 24), followed by the pyrolysis unit. The thermal drying unit will contribute the least to the emissions.

Despite its low heat and electricity output, the current scenario holds promise for product recovery. With a total carbon offset of 13.47 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste from heat of 38.7 MJ and electricity of 7.8 kWh in S8-FL-Pyro, this scenario could be a viable alternative for product recovery, shifting the focus from energy recovery to a more sustainable approach.

S9-FL-BD: Due to the high-fat content in fleshings (7-18%), there is a possibility of using this waste in eco-friendly by-products such as biodiesel, which can be used as a source of green energy.

Figure 26. Model description for biodiesel production (S9-FL-BD)

A study case has been considered to check whether biodiesel production is eco-friendly (Sandhya et al. 2016) , followed by a special pretreatment (to obtain required seize) with an energy requirement of 0.03 kWh/ton of waste in Figure 26 (Bhagwat et al. 2015) . Auxiliary inputs such as methanol for esterification and transesterification, sulphuric acid for esterification, ammonium chloride, hydrochloric acid, and tap water for hydrolysis have been considered, as shown in the inventory (Sandhya et al. 2016; Sousa et al. 2017; Dufour and Iribarren 2012; Kubendran et al. 2017) . The fat-extraction average of 12.5% has been taken (Sandhya et al. 2016) . Heat and electricity are required for fat-extraction stage, esterification, and transesterification, as mentioned in the inventory section (Appendix). A good amount of remaining waste after hydrolysis can be used as fertilizer. Glycerin and biodiesel will be obtained at the end of the process (Dufour and Iribarren 2012) . To get good quality biodiesel, washing (dry) is required, with an energy consumption of 0.049kWh/ton of waste (Alamsyah and Loebis 2014) .

Producing biodiesel can be an optimal sustainable approach (Mozhiarasi et al. 2023) ; a yield of 9.3% of biodiesel and 5.5 % of glycerin is obtained (Sandhya et al. 2016) .

CF: The CF of 200 kg-CO₂eq./ton of fleshings is emitted while producing biodiesel and glycerine. This technique holds promise as a sustainable approach to obtaining high product recovery as compost, biodiesel, and glycerin. However, utilizing chemicals like methanol and heat requirements can make this process unfeasible from an economic point of view.

Figure 27. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in biodiesel

Producing biodiesel requires a considerable amount of heat and electricity, which can be noticed in the CF value of the current scenario. Fat extraction and pretreatment units will be considered the most considerable electricity and heat consumers in the current scenario.

Comparison between all possible scenarios for utilizing fleshings:

Table 10. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S4-FL-AD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	120.46	245	824	165	285	Yes

*Carbon offset is based upon the production of heat and electricity

Table 11. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S5-FL-AD+Pyro)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-225 from CHP	125.7	283	824	165	285	Yes

*Carbon offset is based upon the production of heat and electricity

Table 12. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S6-FL-CO)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	60	268	0	0	Compost	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 13. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S7-FL-OD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	0	1189	-	-	-	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 14. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S8-FL-Pyro)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
1046	131	257	38.7	7.8	13.5	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 15. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S9-FL-BD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
938	54	200	-	-	Biodiesel	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Suitable scenarios can be considered, followed by a sustainable approach based on energy recovery and product recovery to add economic value in Table 10 to Table 15.

The CF order for all scenarios for utilizing fleshings with different solid waste techniques followed as:

$$FL-OD < FL-AD+Pyro < FL-CO < FL-Pyro < FL-AD < FL-BD$$

Producing biodiesel can be a significant replacement for the biodiesel industry. Still, open dumping can be avoided because of its high CF.

Waste 3: Hair waste from tannery

S10-HW-CO+SP: To amend the organic quality in agriculture, composting from hair waste can be an alternative because of the high nitrogen content (16 – 18.3%), which will have an essential role in plant growth because of the slow decomposition of keratin (Barrena et al. 2007a) . To achieve a C: N ratio of compost mixture (mentioned in the inventory section), hair waste and sewage sludge have been taken in a ratio of 1:1. The final compost has a high amount of nitrogen with an organic content of 57.8% (Barrena et al. 2007a) . While analyzing Umberto for hair waste, there is no need for an external aeration supply and machine power because of natural convection (the movement of air or gases within the compost pile due to temperature differences). The data for pre-and post-treatment with shredding and trommel has been taken the same way as in S6-FL-CO.

Considering hair waste as input for static pile composting with substrate raw sewage (Barrena et al. 2007a) , a scenario is performed with the help of moisture and carbon balance (Boldrin et al. 2011) .

Figure 28. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in static pile composting of hair waste

CF: The CF for 10-HW-CO+SP is 160.5 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input hair waste with a compost yield of 52%. This approach can be a very suitable solution for handling hair waste sustainably.

Most of the emission will occur through the CO₂ from the pile during static pile composting operations, followed by energy consumption for pretreatment and mixing.

S11-HW-OD: The high carbon content of 445 kg in 1 ton of hair waste results in a significant amount of methane production. The biodegradability of hair waste is still not included. We have used the total carbon percentage in 1 ton of hair waste to calculate the CH₄ amount.

CF: This process produces a very high CF of 1189 kg-CO₂eq./ton of hair waste. In light of these findings, it is crucial to avoid open dumping of hair waste strictly and instead explore more sustainable management options.

Figure 29. Model description for keratin production from hair waste

S12-HW-KP: Hair waste contains 72 – 72.5 % protein content (Agustini et al. 2018) , which can be a significant source of keratin production. The inventories for pre-treatment and transportation have been taken the same for 1 ton of hair waste (Figure 29). The waste has to hydrolyze in the presence of NaOH with a density of 2.13 g/cm³ (20% of w/v) and water (5 times of waste) at 70°C (Ramya et al. 2022) . The mixture will pass through nylon mesh before it cools down normally. The filtered waste stays in an industrial centrifuge (Ramya et al. 2020) . The time required to separate the solid content from the mixture can be 20 minutes (Da Souza et al. 2022b) . However, the wastewater can be separated and moved to treatment. The soild content has to freeze at - 80°C to get the krystalline powder as output (40gm/l) (Da Souza et al. 2022b) . With its high protein content of 72.8–75.0%, hair waste emerges as an exceptional source for extracting keratin (Table 2).

CF: When performing a hair waste scenario for extracting keratin, the process can produce a CF of up to 165.6 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste. However, with a yield of keratin powder at 40gm/l (4%) of total input materials (Da Souza et al. 2022b) ., this scenario can be viewed as a sustainable product recovery method.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input type="checkbox"/> Hair waste 1x electricity, high voltage transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3 sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state tap water	96.725 82.926 11.745 1.841 0.213	kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq
<input type="checkbox"/> Keratin powder electricity, high voltage sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state tap water	68.873 56.528 11.065 1.279	kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq kg CO2-Eq
<input type="checkbox"/> wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year	0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 30. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S12-HW-KP

Figure 31. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in keratin production

In the current scenario for producing keratin powder, most of the emissions will come from using high electricity in shredding, stirring, and freezing (Figure 31). The remaining emissions will be emitted using NaOH during the hydrolysis phase of hair waste and a lorry during transportation (Figure 30). After comparing previous scenarios, S12-HW-KP is considered the most sustainable approach for product recovery.

Comparison between all possible scenarios for utilizing hair waste:

Table 16. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S10-HW-CO+SP)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	56.8	160.5	-	-	Compost	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 17. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S11-HW-OD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	0	1189	-	-	-	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 18. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S12-HW-CO+KP)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	56.8	165.6	-	-	Keratin powder	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

On comparing all three scenarios of hair waste from Table 16 and Table 18, producing compost and keratin powder can be a suitable approach for product recovery, which adds value to the product.

Waste 4: Chrome shavings & splits

S13-CS-AD & S14-CS-AD+Pyro: In the case of chrome shavings & splits, 1 ton has been fed into an anaerobic digestion chamber, followed by the same amount of energy consumption in pretreatment (shredding) and transportation as mentioned in previous scenarios. As mentioned in the inventory section, most of the data in these two scenarios will be the same as before in the case of fleshings. However, the amount of biogas will differ with the value of 0.375 m³/kg VS, which is lower than the same scenarios in the case of fleshings (Gomes et al. 2019). As a result, the amount of biogas 246 m³ will be achieved. Meanwhile, chrome shavings & splits contain a high amount of total solids (80.3 - 83 %). Further utilization of biogas will be the same as scenarios in fleshings. The digestate can be utilized as input for pyrolysis or discarded as waste (chromium content). While digestate is utilized in pyrolysis, the amount of biochar and bio-oil will be 30% and 49% simultaneously (Velusamy et al. 2020).

CF: The total CF for S13-CS-AD is 331 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste, respectively, with heat of 2760 MJ and electricity of 556 kWh. The digestate yield is found to be 50 %. Considering chrome shavings & splits as tanning waste, it is impossible to use digestate as compost for agricultural practices.

While considering the pyrolysis unit with the AD process for chrome shavings & splits, the CF footprint is 565 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste with 14% biochar and 23.5 % bio-oil from input waste followed by the AD process. The exact amount of energy will be obtained due to the identical model setup in both scenarios.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather waste	16.737	kg CO2-Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	4.992	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg (GLO, market for heat, central or	266.857	kg CO2-Eq
lubricating oil	154.537	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	104.960	kg CO2-Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	7.360	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Semidreid digestate	47.681	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	47.681	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10/year	0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 32. Overview of the amount of emissions emitted from entries in S13-CS-AD

Entries	Quantity	Unit
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Leather waste	16.737	kg CO2-Eq
transport, freight, lorry 3.5-7.5 metric ton, EURO3	11.745	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	4.992	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biochar for further use	208.352	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	96.960	kg CO2-Eq
lubricating oil	58.685	kg CO2-Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	24.770	kg CO2-Eq
Methane, fossil	18.403	kg CO2-Eq
Carbon dioxide, fossil	6.740	kg CO2-Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	2.795	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Biooil	340.309	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	158.368	kg CO2-Eq
lubricating oil	95.852	kg CO2-Eq
heat, district or industrial, natural gas	40.457	kg CO2-Eq
Methane, fossil	30.058	kg CO2-Eq
Carbon dioxide, fossil	11.009	kg CO2-Eq
sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	4.565	kg CO2-Eq
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10/year	0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 33. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S14-CS-AD+Pyro

After comparing the results for entries in both current scenarios, it has been observed that utilizing biogas as an energy source requires more electricity in CHP unit, as shown in Figure 32 and Figure 33. Adding pyrolysis in the AD process can increase energy consumption in the case of chrome waste, which contradicts the scenarios S4-FL-AD & S5-FL-AD+Pyro in the

case of fleshings. This scenario also shows how the amount of volatile solids in the leather waste can change energy consumption. Most emissions will come from the CHP unit (Figure 34), while chrome shaving is utilized in the AD process.

Figure 34. Overview of the amount of emissions from each process in S13-CS-AD & S14-CS-AD+Pyro

Considering the same amount of energy production from CHP units in both scenarios, a carbon offset of 960 kg-CO₂eq./ton has been credited to the grid. In both cases, AD with a CHP unit can be a good alternative for energy recovery.

In addition, S13-CS-AD can be considered an optimal solution for chrome shavings & splits in energy recovery. Meanwhile, S14-CS-AD+Pyro can be regarded as a good energy and product recovery scenario.

S15-CS-OD: With a high carbon content of 352.6 kg per ton, chrome shaving has a high potential to produce more methane, which will depend solely on the only degradable carbon in chrome shavings.

CF: Chrome shavings & splits dumped openly will produce a high CF of 839.5 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste. Considering the sustainable approach, landfills should be avoided strictly in this scenario.

S16-CS-Pyro.: A moisture of 17% has been considered, which is in the optimal range for pyrolysis. No dewatering and thermal drying is required. A scenario with a pyrolysis unit (including CHP) for Chrome shavings & splits has been performed. The additional CHP unit will convert the Pyro gas to heat and electricity. The biogas compressor in the CHP unit requires energy to run.

In addition, a CHP unit also requires fuels like natural gas, biogas, diesel, or waste oils to generate electricity and heat efficiently. The amount of energy the CHP unit produces will depend upon the LHV of gas that has entered it.

CF: Because of the input material's high solid content, the current scenario's CF is 541 kg-CO₂eq./ton of chrome shavings & splits..

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste		131.334	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pyrolysis		119.589	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Transport		11.745	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biochar		35.877	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pyrolysis		35.877	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Biooil		58.599	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Pyrolysis		58.599	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, low voltage (IN-Northern grid, electricity voltage transformation from medium to low voltage, CHP unit)		132.459	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, central or small-scale, natural gas, Jakobsberg (GLO, market for heat, central or small-scale, natural CHP unit)		182.871	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 35. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in S16-CS-Pyro

Figure 36. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in S16-CS-Pyro

In the current scenario, most emissions will be produced by energy consumption in Figure 35 and lubricating oil in the CHP unit in Figure 36.

Utilizing a CHP after pyrolysis can produce heat of 911 MJ and electricity of 183 kWh. Considering the carbon offset approach, a total of 316 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste has been forwarded to the grid and taken as an energy recovery scenario.

After comparing the results, it can be noticed that the current scenario can be an optimal solution for handling chrome shavings & splits. 30% for biochar and 49% for biooil can be obtained. Our study focused on handling pyrogas, which can create high carbon emissions. To avoid those emissions, the pyrogas has been utilized through a CHP unit, which can reduce the actual carbon emissions. Products like biochar and bio-oil at the end of the pyrolysis are considered valuable outputs.

S17-CS-LS: Chrome shavings can be used as leather board and natural polymer leather sheets or composite (Senthil et al. 2015; Senthil et al. 2022; Senthil et al. 2023). In Figure 37, the mixture of papermill sludge with natural rubber latex 300 mL w/v (density of 60 kg /m³) with 2% ethylene glycol has been blended and pressed with a hydraulic machine with 800 psi for 15 seconds and later sundried for 6 hr, (Senthil et al. 2023).

Figure 37. Model description for making leather sheet from chrome shavings

. Later, the same material was cast into 3*4 feet of sheet and pressed with 1500 psi for 15 seconds in a heat press machine. The final amount of weight has been discovered in a natural polymer leather sheet (16% of the initial weight) after different tests such as Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) and Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA) (Senthil et al. 2023b) .

CF: Considering the recycling of chrome waste into valuable products such as leather sheets, the total carbon footprint is 333 kg-CO₂eq./ton of waste is evaluated.

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
sludge from pulp and paper production (RoW, treatment, sludge from pulp and paper)		0.187	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 1		0.187	kg CO2-Eq
Chrome shavings		2.994	kg CO2-Eq
Transport		2.808	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 1		0.187	kg CO2-Eq
Mixed solution		329.940	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 2		218.888	kg CO2-Eq
Pressing 800 psi for 15s		65.579	kg CO2-Eq
Pressing 1500 psi for 15s		45.249	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 1		0.224	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year (Mixing 1 - WWTP)		0.000	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year (Mixing 1 - WWTP)		0.000	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year (Pressing 800 psi for 15s - WWTP)		0.000	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10l/year (Pressing 800 psi for 15s - WWTP)		0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 38. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in S17-CS-LS

Figure 39. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in producing leather sheet

In current scenarios, most of the emissions will come from using latex through mixing, followed by electricity consumption in processes like pressing (Figure 39). This approach can result in sustainable product recovery from waste. The same model is followed when making leather boards from buffing dust. Making a board from chrome waste can be a very sustainable approach because of the production processes followed by a few steps, such as mixing, pressing, and sun-drying.

As a valuable product recovery process, this scenario can be considered the optimal solution for separating chrome shavings into leather sheets.

S18-CS-INCI: To check the impacts on the environment of chrome waste utilizing the incineration technique, a scenario has been developed.

Figure 40. Model description for incineration of chrome shavings & splits (S18-CS-INCI)

The whole assembly, including the Waste disposal pit, feed hopper with crane, Moving grate, furnace followed by conveyor belt and boiler, fabric filter baghouse for gas purification, and induced fan before stack (Figure 40), has been adapted from (Quina et al. 2011) . The amount of energy required to run the waste handle crane and moving grate has been mentioned in Appendix.

To run the model for accurate results, there is a need for input auxiliary materials such as activated carbon, diesel, electricity, lime, limestone, sodium carbonate, and urea, followed by blast furnace slag and bottom ash from the furnace as output, which can be directly disposed of in landfill (out of system boundary) (Bianco et al. 2021b; Liu et al. 2017) . The heat produced through the furnace will be transferred to the boiler, contributing to heat production (Quina et al. 2011) . The number of gases emitted through the stack with the forced-induced fan will majorly contribute to the environmental burden. The amount of total emissions has been discussed previously in the inventory section (Bianco et al. 2021b) . The same reduction is considered, up to 93%, with chrome waste, like shavings and finishings waste, with 7% incinerated ash (Velusamy et al. 2020) .

CF: The CF for chrome shavings & splits is 301 kg-CO₂eq./ton of waste, which can be considered a solution for sustainably handling the waste.

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste		301.027	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Furnace		210.751	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Induced draft fan		58.425	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Moving grate		14.556	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Feed hooper		11.303	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Fabric filter baghouse		3.184	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Transport by lorry		2.808	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (RoW, h		0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 41. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Leather waste	301.027	kg CO ₂ -Eq
electricity, high voltage	202.161	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Carbon dioxide, fossil	55.986	kg CO ₂ -Eq
sodium bicarbonate	22.159	kg CO ₂ -Eq
activated carbon, granular	6.992	kg CO ₂ -Eq
urea	5.172	kg CO ₂ -Eq
transport, freight, lorry with reefer, cooling	2.808	kg CO ₂ -Eq
fly ash and scrubber sludge	2.705	kg CO ₂ -Eq
Carbon dioxide, from soil or biomass stock	1.960	kg CO ₂ -Eq
diesel	0.741	kg CO ₂ -Eq
bottom ash, MSWI-WWT, WW, average	0.344	kg CO ₂ -Eq
heat, district or industrial, other than natural gas (RoW, heat, from municipal waste incinerator	0.000	kg CO ₂ -Eq

Figure 42. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in incineration

Most of the emission will come from the energy consumption in the furnace (Figure 41), followed by emissions from stack.

Considering carbon offset for this approach, a total of 5.6 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste has been forwarded to the grid. The most significant contribution to getting a high carbon footprint in incineration is flue gases after burning the waste.

Comparison between all possible scenarios for utilizing chrome shavings:

Table 19. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S13-CS-AD)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	137	331	2760	556	960.42	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 20. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S14-CS-AD+Pyro)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	197	565	2760	556	960.42	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 21. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S14-CS-OD)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	-	839.5	-	-	-	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 22. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S16-CS-Pyro)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
0	169	541	911	183	316	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 23. : Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S17-CS-LS)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	15	333	-	-	Leather sheet	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 24. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S18-CS-INCI)

Input energy		Current CF	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)	Including all flows	Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	118	301	1600		5.6	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Comparing all possible scenarios for utilizing chrome shavings & splits (Table 19 and Table 24), AD, AD+ pyrolysis, and pyrolysis (solely) can be considered the optimal solution for energy recovery.

Meanwhile, S18-CS-INCI can be considered a solution for mitigating chrome waste by burning. However, this system can't be considered an optimal energy and product recovery solution in the current scenario. It does not add significant values for fly ash or other output products. In this study, a treatment for fly ash is not considered. This system can be regarded as feasible for handling high input waste in case of a total reduction of solids in waste with heat production through boilers.

In addition, S14-CS-OD can be considered as the worst scenario. Considering product recovery from waste, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, and S17-CS-LS can be regarded as optimal solutions for recovering products such as biochar, bio-oil, and leather sheet or board.

Waste 5: Buffing dust

S19-BD-OD: Considering the high carbon content of 393.7 kg in buffing dust, this scenario will provide the same result as in the previous scenario of open dumping for other waste.

CF: This scenario can be avoided strictly due to the high CF of 839.5 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste

S20-BD-BO: Considering the study case for buffing dust for producing leather board (Senthil et al. 2015; Senthil et al. 2022; Senthil et al. 2023b), natural latex rubber with a density of 60 kg/m³ is used.

Figure 43. Model description for making leather board (S20-BD-BO)

The remaining data for making the board will be the same as for making a leather sheet from chrome savings with the same composition.

CF: Considering buffing dust into a valuable product such as a leather board, the total CF while making a leather board is 344.5 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste.

Entries	Quantity	Unit
Buffing dust	0.051	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	0.051	kg CO2-Eq
Mixed solution	344.408	kg CO2-Eq
latex	221.700	kg CO2-Eq
electricity, high voltage	102.172	kg CO2-Eq
ethylene glycol	20.480	kg CO2-Eq
tap water	0.058	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10/year	0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 44. Overview of the amount of emissions from entries in leather board

Processes	Share	Quantity	Unit
Buffing dust		0.051	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 1		0.051	kg CO2-Eq
Mixed solution		344.408	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 2		242.179	kg CO2-Eq
Pressing 1000opsi for 5s		62.682	kg CO2-Eq
Pressing 2000opsi for 10s		39.490	kg CO2-Eq
Mixing 1		0.058	kg CO2-Eq
wastewater treatment facility, capacity 1.1E10/year		0.000	kg CO2-Eq

Figure 45. Overview of the amount of emissions from processes in leather board

Producing leather boards can be the optimal solution for handling buffing dust. The only emissions from making the leather board will come from electricity consumption and latex input in the mixing - 2 process, as shown in Figure 44 and Figure 45. The carbon offset has been compared in the next section.

S21-BD-Pyro: Considering the buffing dust with solid contents of 87.5%, this waste is ideal for pyrolysis. The parameters for pyrolysis and CHP unit have been considered the same scenario S16-CS- Pyro.

CF: The CF of 372 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste has been achieved through pyrolysis. The CF value has been obtained lower than that of chrome shavings & splits because only 20% of pyrolysis gas has been utilized in the CHP unit. The mass recovery has been discussed in

Waste 6: Crust trimmings

S22-CT-OD: The only possible scenario for crust trimmings to conduct an LCA study is to dispose carefully. Meanwhile, Buffing dust consists of 583.77 kg of carbon content, which can have a high amount of biodegradable or non-biodegradable carbon. In the current study, only biodegradable carbon has been considered. Assuming the whole carbon content is uniform, it is to be considered to find out the emission out of it.

CF: The CF of crust trimmings is highest at 839.5 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste in all leather waste considered in the current thesis. Following a sustainable approach, landfills for crust trimmings must be strictly avoided. The exact value of the carbon footprint for finishing waste is considered in S25-FTW- OD.

Comparison between all possible scenarios for utilizing chrome shavings:

Table 25. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S19-BD-OD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	-	839.5	-	-	-	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 26. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S20-BD-BO & S21-BD-Pyro)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Scenario	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
S20-BD-BO	60	344.5	-	-	Leather board	Yes
S21-BD-Pyro	145	372	976	196	338	Yes

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Table 27. Comparison between current CF and Carbon offset from energy balance (S22-CT-OD)

Input energy		Current CF Including all flows	Output energy		Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ eq./ FU)	Remarks as a sustainable approach
Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		Heat (MJ)	Electricity (kWh)		
-	-	839.5	-	-	-	Avoided

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

Waste 7: Finishing trimmings waste

S23-FTW-Pyro: Considering leather finishing waste, a moisture content of 13% has been considered, which requires no additional drying process. For further utilization, the current scenario will be followed the same as S16-CS-Pyro.

CF: The CF for finishing waste can reach 541 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste, with heat of 910 MJ and electricity of 183 kWh. Following a sustainable approach, pyrolysis for finishing waste can be an excellent alternative to recover energy and products.

S24-FTW-INCI: Considering the same inventories for finished trimmings to utilize in the incineration process, the same GWP has been obtained, followed by the same reduction in the mass of input waste, which is considered in scenario S18-CS-INCI. A comparison of energy offsets, like crust trimmings, has been followed in finished trimmings. The only change, as different energy offsets for heat production, will come from incineration because of different calorific values between chrome shavings and finished trimmings, as shown in Table 28.

4.2 Total CFs with mass and energy recovery (by sustainable approach)

In current study, leather waste is methodically converted into product and energy through treatments like AD process, composting, pyrolysis, incineration, or product-based techniques. These strategies seek to support the production of renewable energy, minimize waste that ends up in open dumping, and cut down on greenhouse gas emissions to maintain long-term ecological balance, resource efficiency, and community well-being. The CFs for each scenario have been mentioned with carbon offset and performance.

We followed two criteria to compare the models' performances according to their CF values (lack of LCA study on leather waste treatment).

- Energy offset (calculated already in each possible scenario)
- The CF values from open dumping and by UNIDO (Appendix)

Table 28. The global impact from each scenario with their perspective treatment in terms of CFs followed by energy and mass recoveries

S.No.	Model scenarios	CFs (kg-CO ₂ /ton)	Energy recovery	Mass recovery	Carbon offset* (kg-CO ₂ /ton)
1	S1- RT-AD	293	✓	Yes	471
2	S2-RT-OD	1189	✗	No	-
3	S3-RT-GP	342	✗	Yes	-
4	S4-FL-AD	245	✓	Yes	285
5	S5-FL-AD+Pyro	283	✓	Yes	285
6	S6-FL-CO	268	✗	Yes	-
7	S7-FL- OD	1189	✗	No	-
8	S8-FL-Pyro	257	✓	Yes	13
9	S9-FL-BD	200	✗	Yes	-
10	S10-HW-CO+SP	160.5	✗	Yes	-
11	S11-HW- OD	1189	✗	No	-
12	S12-HW-KP	165.6	✗	Yes	-
13	S13-CS-AD	331	✓	Yes	960
14	S14-CS-AD+Pyro	565	✓	Yes	960
15	S15-CS- OD	839.5	✗	No	-
16	S16-CS-Pyro	541	✓	Yes	316
17	S17-CS-LS	333	✗	Yes	-
18	S18-CS-INCI	301	✓	No	5.6
19	S19-BD- OD	839.5	✗	No	-
20	S20-BD-BO	344.5	✗	Yes	-
21	S21-BD-Pyro	372	✓	Yes	339
22	S22-CT- OD	839.5	✗	No	-
23	S23-FTW-Pyro	541	✓	Yes	316
24	S24-FTW-INCI	300	✓	No	4.3
25	S25-FTW- OD	839.5	✗	No	-

*Carbon offset is based on the production of heat and electricity

As shown in Table 28, the scenarios that produce energy as output are to be considered efficient treatments. Treatments like AD and AD with pyrolysis are optimal for handling raw trimmings, fleshings, and chrome shavings. The finding behind the high energy production is methane yield in each process. The initial amount of biogas yields was taken from literature, as shown in the Appendix. The scenarios from Table 28 are entirely based on the

energy balance at the end of each treatment. Meanwhile, scenarios like the pyrolysis process for fleshings do show a minimal amount of carbon offset. This scenario is due to the high moisture content (80%) present in fleshings, which can be removed with the help of the thermal drying technique.

The scenarios, such as incineration for chrome shavings & splits and finished trimmings, show the highest weight reduction. The heat produced from these scenarios is considerably minor, with low carbon offsets. These incineration scenarios are considered to be promising. No carbon balance is calculated for scenarios entirely based on the product yield, such as gelatin, keratin, biodiesel, leather sheet, and leather board.

In addition, scenarios like open dumping contradict the carbon balance. The total carbon in solids will be responsible for high methane yield from dumping sites.

4.2.1 Best combinations for Energy recovery

While preparing the literature review, only three journals were found for the LCA study on hair waste and biodiesel production from fleshings, which inhibits the comparison of recovered energy between the carbon balance from different leather waste and our study. The MSW (energy recovery) and CF data from UNIDO have been considered for a fair comparison (Buljan 2017).

Figure 46. Performance of selected scenarios based on the energy recovery

Through anaerobic digestion, the scenarios utilized fleshings, raw trimmings, and chrome shavings. Combining the total emissions for this leather waste, the least CF of 245 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste is obtained in fleshings in AD process. The highest CF of 331 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste was calculated in chrome shavings & splits in AD process (Table 28).

However, the CF for kitchen waste (biowaste) was stated to be 370 kg-CO₂eq./ton of waste followed by energy consumption from burning biogas with the help of a CHP unit (Slorach et al. 2019). The current scenario for fleshings results aligns with this study, considering the same solids content in biowaste for MSW and fleshings. The amount of biogas for

kitchen waste is 137 m³ /ton of input waste. The remaining amount of energy, 254 kWh, has been forwarded to the grid.

In addition, a range of CF of 251 to 646 kg-CO₂eq./ton of MSW waste with 53% moisture has been performed (Malakahmad et al. 2017). They have also provided anaerobic digestion and recycling techniques, avoiding plastic, glass, and textile waste for recycling purposes. This resulted in 489 kg-CO₂eq./ton of MSW waste with food, yard, and paper waste for the AD process. No LCA study was found for AD with biowaste with a solid content of 80% or more.

The current study performed the scenarios for AD (discussed earlier), AD with pyrolysis & pyrolysis processes. It has been noticed in pyrolysis scenarios that the highest CF is 541 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste is obtained for chrome-based waste, such as chrome shavings & splits in S16-CS-Pyro and finished trimmings in S22-FTW-Pyro, followed by fleshings in S8-FL-Pyro with a CF of 257 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste (Table 28). On the other hand, S14-CS-AD+Pyro is the optimal solution for chrome shavings & splits from an energy recovery perspective. Comparing scenarios based on product recovery, such as digestate, biochar, and bio-oil, are discussed in the next section as complete mass reduction. The results indicate the following order based on CFs (Table 28).

S8-FL-Pyro < S5-FL-AD+Pyro < S16-CS-Pyro = S23-FTW-Pyro < S21-BD-Pyro < S14-CS-AD+Pyro

In comparing current solid waste technique results with MSW literature (Wang et al. 2021), scenario two has been performed with a pyrolysis unit. The results were in units of total environmental impact (TEI). However, the results indicate the following order of impact on the environment.

Py-AD < Py < AD < AD-Py

In addition, fast pyrolysis was performed while keeping the goal of achieving the bio-oil from municipal waste with 40% of water content (Wang et al. 2021). Only 10% of the moisture of initial waste has been considered before entering the pyrolysis unit. The assembly is equipped with bio-oil upgrading, which requires more energy with high gasoline-based vehicle operations (531 kg CO₂eq./ton of input waste). The total CF has been evaluated with 1250 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste, which is considered a high-emitting emissions technique.

Meanwhile, a pyrolysis-gasification scenario was performed for municipal waste, which resulted in a high CF of 1017 kg-CO₂ eq./ton of input waste (Zaman 2013). The high carbon footprint is due to the temperature range of both techniques. Pyrolysis requires around temperatures of 400–1,000 °C, but gasification is performed at 1000 – 1400 °C, which requires more energy consumption. Meanwhile, an LCA study of pyrolysis was also conducted on energy crops, forest residues, and agricultural residues (Gahane et al. 2022). Meanwhile, (Heng et al. 2018) also examined the carbon footprint of pyrolysis on corn remains from crops in terms of energy (MJ) as output.

Incineration is considered a sustainable approach because it reduces the organic component of total solids. Two scenarios for incineration were performed for chrome shavings & splits in S18-CS-INCI and finished trimmings in S24-FTW-INCI. The setup for incineration for each stage has been adopted with different energy consumption parameters, as mentioned in inventories (Bianco et al. 2021a). The consistent CF values arise due to the absence of data entries in the ecoinvent database for emissions from stacks, specifically for pollutants such as sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, carbon monoxide, and particulate matter. Only carbon dioxide emissions have been accounted for in the current scenarios. The calorific value for 15.7 MJ/kg in S18-CS-INCI and 19.9 MJ/kg in S24-FTW-INCI have been considered (Appendix).

No LCA study was found in the literature on incineration for handling chrome shavings and finished trimmings in energy production. We have adopted the data from different literature, as shown in Table 39. Only calorific values for chrome shavings and finished trimming have been considered for their respective emissions Table 39.

S18-CS-INCI & S24-FTW-INCI can be compared with the MSW literature, followed by the incineration technique to reduce leather waste. A CF of 646 t CO₂ eq./t MSW was found (Malakahmad et al. 2017). 25.77% of food waste has been considered, followed by plastic 22% and 7.73 % of textile waste.

In addition, a CF of 290 kg-CO₂ eq./ton of input MSW waste without credit was also reported (Jeswani et al. 2013).

4.2.2 Best combinations for complete mass reduction/product recovery

Figure 47. Mass recovery from as digestate from S1- RT-AD, S4-FL-AD & S13-CS-AD

In comparing the yield in the anaerobic digestion (AD) process, digestate production from raw trimmings yielded up to 325 kg, followed by a dewatering ratio and a high biogas yield (Figure 47). Conversely, fleshings yielded up to 185 kg of digestate with a lower biogas yield, as discussed earlier.

In the case of S13-CS-AD, chrome shavings & splits yield a higher amount of digestate containing up to 82% solids, followed by 18% dewatering ratio (Gomes et al. 2019). The same parameters will be followed in case of yield of biochar and bio-oil from different

leather waste in S5-FL-AD+Pyro, S8-FL-Pyro, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S21-BD-Pyro & S23-FTW-Pyro.

Figure 48. Mass recovery as biochar from S5-FL-AD+Pyro, S8-FL-Pyro, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S21-BD-Pyro, & S22-FTW-Pyro.

Figure 49. Mass recovery as bio-oil from S5-FL-AD+Pyro, S8-FL-Pyro, S14-CS-AD+Pyro, S16-CS-Pyro, S21-BD-Pyro, & S22-FTW-Pyro

The yield percentages from the Appendix explain the proximate biochar and bio-oil recovery in S14-CS-AD+Pyro and S23-FTW-Pyro.

Solid-state fermentation and composting (In-vessel) were performed for 100 kg of raw hides and 13.7 kg of hair waste. The CF was not discussed (Catalán et al. 2017b). Considering suitable moisture and carbon balance (Boldrin et al. 2011), the study cases have been performed for fleshings and hair waste. For fleshings, the input materials and final compost percentage have been taken in S6-FL-CO (Hashem et al. 2024b).

In the case of hair waste for performing composting, the input material and compost percentage have been taken. A CF of 268 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input waste is obtained in S10-HW-CO+SP (Barrena et al. 2007a). In the case of hair waste, it is possible to use the hair waste with de-linking sludge from the tannery and municipal wastewater in a ratio of 1:1, 1:2, and 1:4, possibly to have 52.85% of compost. No data on hair waste was found for N, P, or K (Barrena et al. 2007a).

Compared with the literature on composting, a CF of 196 kg-CO₂eq./ton of input organic fraction of municipal waste (OFMSW) was reported for turned windrow composting. They

also considered various types of composting with resultant carbon emissions, such as home composting with 209 kg-CO₂eq./ton of OFMSW and confined windrows with 123 kg-CO₂eq./ton of OFMSW (Colón et al. 2012) .

In addition, an LCA study on tunnel and confined windrow composting was performed, with carbon footprints of 64 and 63 kg-CO₂eq./ton of OFMSW, respectively (Erasmio Cadena et al. 2009) .

A LCA study on tilapia residues for gelatin production. Scenario (A) is considered without mechanically separating meat (MSM) from tilapia residues, followed by a series of treatments, such as hydrolysis. Scenario (B) followed no separation of MSM, followed by the same treatment in scenario (A). This study was based on a laboratory experiment on 1 gram of residues (Sampaio et al. 2017) . CF is considered a measurement unit of carbon emissions. 0.0437 and 0.0853 kg-CO₂eq./gm of input residues. These scenarios show a very high CF compared to our current study for leather waste. Meanwhile, the current study's yield for gelatin from raw trimmings has recovered to 172 kg on a total solids basis. Comparing the yield with price, gelatin holds a good market value.

In the case of biodiesel production, an LCA study was performed on producing biofuel from fleshings. But data must be available online (Kılıç et al. 2013) . Meanwhile, a study was conducted on multiple scenarios (only scenarios relatable to our study), such as Biodiesel from beef tallow and Biodiesel from poultry fat with a CF of 16.97 kg-CO₂eq./ 1GJ of energy, respectively (Dufour and Iribarren 2012) . No LCA was found when making leather sheets or boards.

4.3 Climate change (greenhouse impact)

“Greenhouse gases” (GHGs) refer to the gases that can evolve from different stages of the utilization process for leather waste. GHGs mainly consist of water vapor, methane, and nitrous oxide, which will accumulate in Earth’s atmosphere and reduce heat loss into space. This process will add to the accumulated impact of these gases, enhancing the global temperature, which is called the greenhouse effect over 100 years (Feo and Malvano 2009) .

This thesis is about waste management or product-based techniques. In our study, boundaries were set as “ gate to gate,” which defines the entry of leather waste into the waste management system and its transformation into energy or products. Waste management treatments can suppress the overall impact of CF on the environment but can also recommend a sustainable pathway (Bernstad and La Cour Jansen 2012) . Considering CO₂, CH₄, and N₂O gases with their CF values can accommodate the total CF from each scenario in the current study.

4.4 Limitations

Only gases responsible for climate change can have an overall impact from using waste as energy or a product. In our study, we must add what other gases can improve the overall CF. The total biodegradable carbon in leather waste has to be considered except in the AD

process. The emissions and losses from the AD process in terms of energy and mass balance have been considered. In the case of composting of fleshings and hair waste, only CO₂ gas was considered according to their carbon balance during the process, followed by moisture balance, which can be improved further by considering remaining gases like CH₄ and N₂O. Utilization through pyrolysis and incineration was wholly based on the literature. The new LHVs for pyrolysis gas were calculated and matched with their respective scenarios. Our study considers biochar and bio-oil as part of mass recovery. These products can also improve the current CFs in our study. Meanwhile, only pyrolysis gas was considered in our study and fed to the CHP unit in the pyrolysis scenario to check how much energy could be produced. Other outputs, such as biochar and bio-oil, have been recovered as products for further utilization.

Products like gelatin, biodiesel, keratin, glycerin, and leather board were created based on complete assumptions and experimental data from the literature, as shown in the Appendix. Their physicochemical balance should have been addressed during the study.

In the case of open dumping, the EPFR model is solely based on the waste's total biodegradable carbon content. This can be considered for further examination of the emissions from open dumping.

5. Conclusion

This thesis evaluated the possible treatments for each leather waste to find a suitable approach to recover energy from leather wastes with a little focus on mass recovery. The evaluation is based on based on the total carbon emissions through different leather waste treatment technologies, and the results are predicted as the total carbon footprint. The best scenarios for energy recovery (carbon offsets) have been discussed earlier in section 4.2.1. The data from UNIDO is used to compare the feasibility of models in terms of CF (Buljan 2017) .

- **Raw trimmings:** With a range of CFs from 293 to 342 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste without considering open dumping as suggested by IPCC and landfill by UNIDO.

Table 29. Status of the scenarios performed for raw trimmings

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Mass recovery(kg)	Performance
AD process	293	471	325**	✓
Open dumping	1189	-	-	Avoided
Gelatin production	342	-	172	✓
UNIDO 2017*	624	-	-	Comparison

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017) , ** Digestate after complete moisture removal

As we compare the CF values for raw trimmings, the minimum emissions come from the AD process, which is also considered an optimal solution for energy recovery. Given its market worth and production output of 172 kg, gelatin (non-edible) is an excellent choice for economic integration. Although the water and chemical consumption is high, considering the commercial application of the product. Utilizing leather waste for gelatin production could be more economically viable and is also comparatively more beneficial than open dumping/landfilling in terms of carbon footprint. The next potential option is the AD process for energy generation, which is the most environmentally benign in terms of carbon footprint.

- **Fleshings:** A range of CFs from 200 to 283 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste is obtained. Since leather fleshings are one of the most researched waste materials, various treatment methods can transform them into valuable goods such as digestate and energy. In the AD process, this waste can provide a carbon offset of up to 285 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste by recovering energy, followed by an upgradation by CHP unit to convert biogas into energy in current study. Fleshings, with considerable fat content, can offer substantial potential for biodiesel generation however it can also be used to produce bio-oil and biochar by pyrolysis. The highest bio-oil output (60%) was achieved at 600°C during pyrolysis with a higher heating value (HHV) of 39.36 MJ/kg, making it a viable biofuel. Biochar, with its elemental composition, can be utilized as a fertilizer. The syngas from pyrolysis of fleshings are measured as 10 MJ/m³, highlighting their potential utility (Appendix).

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Biochar/digestate/ compost(kg)	Bio-oil/ biodiesel (kg)	Performance
AD process	245	285	185**	-	✓
AD+Pyrolysis	283	285	15	25	✓
Composting	268	-	1057#	-	✓
Open dumping	1189	-	na	-	Avoided
Pyrolysis	257	13	130	210	✓
Biodiesel production	200	-	-	93	✓
UNIDO 2017*	624	-	-	-	Comparison

Table 30. Status of the scenarios performed for fleshings

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017) , ** Digestate after complete moisture removal ' # Total of 1556kg of initial input

In addition, comparing CF values from the current study suggests that most treatments utilize fleshings as a potential energy and product source. Meanwhile, with its high CF value, open dumping can be considered the most avoidable scenario. Other options can be adopted based on the site conditions and waste availability, with the targeted market value of the outputted product regionally.

- **Hair waste:** A range of CFs from 160.5 to 165.6 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste is obtained.

Table 31. Status of the scenarios performed for hair waste

Model scenarios	CFs	Mass recovery (kg)	Performance
Composting	160.5	1057**	✓
Open dumping	1189	-	Avoided
Keratin production (dry)	165.6	240	✓
UNIDO 2017*	373	-	Comparison

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017) , ** with 1000kg of raw sewage and required moisture

Hair waste, with its high carbon content, can create much more compost than other waste types. In our investigation, composting 1000 kg of hair waste with 1000 kg of raw sewage can yield 1057 kg of compost. The static pile composting of hair waste produces a CF of about 160.5 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste. Emissions primarily occur during the pretreatment phase, with extra CO₂ emissions occurring during composting.

The production of keratin powder generates a CF of 165.6 kg-CO₂/ton of input. Most emissions originate from the hydrolysis of hair waste and the necessary shredding pretreatment. Meanwhile, given the high CF of hair waste, open dumping should be severely prohibited. A comparative investigation shows that creating compost and keratin powder are much more environmentally beneficial means of managing hair waste.

- **Chrome shavings & splits:** A range of CFs from 301 to 565 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste is obtained.

Although chrome shavings have a higher CF through different treatments than fleshings and raw trimmings, this approach is still suitable as it produces more biochar and bio-oil

due to its higher solid content and low moisture, making it a better alternative to open dumping/landfilling.

Table 32. Status of the scenarios performed for chrome shavings & splits

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Biochar/ digestate (kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
AD process	331	960	497**	-	✓
AD+Pyrolysis	565	960	143	235	✓
Open dumping	839.5	-	-	-	Avoided
Pyrolysis	541	316	300	490	✓
Leather sheet (153 kg)	333	-	-	-	✓
Incineration	301	5.6	-	-	✓
UNIDO 2017*	221	-	-	-	Comparison

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017) ** Digestate after complete moisture removal

Producing leather sheets from chrome shavings is also a possible option. However, using latex, which has a predefined high CF value by the ecoinvent database, could significantly increase the overall CF up to 333 kg-CO₂/ton of input in the current study. Meanwhile, the incineration of chrome shavings, which requires significant electricity to achieve a weight reduction of up to 93%, results in a CF of 301 kg-CO₂/ton of input. When this CF is compared to the open landfiling, it is observed that most of the treatments can be used.

- **Buffing dust:** A range of CFs from 344.5 to 372 kg-CO₂/ton of input waste is obtained.

Table 33 Status of the scenarios performed for buffing dust

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Biochar (kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
Leather board (268 kg)	344.5	-	-	-	✓
Pyrolysis	372	338	375	151	✓
Open dumping	839.5	-	-	-	Avoided
UNIDO 2017*	221	-	-	-	Comparison

CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017)

Using the same criteria as for chrome shavings, the process of producing leather board from buffing dust has a CF of 344.5 kg-CO₂/ton of input. Considering pyrolysis as treatment solution, the utilisation of buffing dust provides CF of up to 372 kg-CO₂/ton of input. The lower value of CF indicates that the pyrolysis gas fed to the CHP unit is 20%. Due to the lack of alternative treatments for buffing dust, leather board manufacturing and pyrolysis appear to be the only environmentally benign solutions compared to open dumping. However, these approaches have a significant CF compared to the benchmarks provided by UNIDO because the use of latex in leather board manufacturing and energy consumption in pyrolysis largely share the resultant CF.

- **Crust trimmings:**

Table 34. Status of the scenarios performed for crust trimmings

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Performance
Open dumping	839.5	-	×
UNIDO 2017*	221	-	Comparison

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017)*

The shortfall of existing research data is observed for crust trimming waste treatment. Often, treatments for finished trimmings are reportedly adopted for treating crust trimmings. Of course, both of these wastes are chrome-tanned, dyed, and dried, while the finished trimmings involve additional coating of a protective layer to the surface of the leather to ensure proper finishing. Hence, the treatments opted for finished trimmings can be applied to crust trimmings as well.

- **Finished trimmings:**

Table 35. Status of the scenarios performed for finished trimmings

Model scenarios	CFs	Carbon offset	Biochar (kg)	Bio-oil (kg)	Performance
Incineration	300	4.3	na	na	✓
Pyrolysis	541	316	270	520	✓
Open dumping	839.5	na	na	na	Avoided
UNIDO 2017*	na	na	na	na	Comparison

*CF data for UNIDO * (Buljan 2017)*

There is no UNIDO benchmark to compare the resultant CF for finished trimmings. However, with the modeled options in the current study, incineration shows a comparatively lower CF and has been found to reduce waste volume, making it a preferable option.

Finally, this study's findings indicate the sustainability of leather waste treatments and prospective avenues for improving sustainability in the leather processing industry. Comparable CFs associated with current treatment methods highlight severe environmental challenges from a life cycle perspective, but they also suggest opportunities for improvement through optimized waste processing procedures. LCA data from the literature are essential for establishing a baseline scenario for each treatment process, supporting the validity of our study, and guiding future research trends in this domain. This study defines environmental trends and identifies gaps in the utilization of leather waste. Significant variations exist in the environmental performance data for leather waste across different tanneries, underscoring the importance of understanding these variations to identify best practices for waste management.

The primary goal of this study is to find the most suitable solution for handling leather waste sustainably. The variability in the results demonstrates that the output of our scenarios correlates with LCA results of standard waste treatment.

Additionally, producing gelatin from raw trimmings emerges as a promising strategy to maximize market value. Alternatives such as glycerin, keratin, biodiesel, and leather board

show competitive market potential and offer feasible options for effective leather waste management.

By increasing the profitability of byproducts and adhering to circular economy concepts, the leather processing industry can improve its sustainability credentials while contributing to the SDG's. Future research should focus on enhancing these approaches and executing comprehensive LCA to guide evidence-based policymaking and industry decisions.

In summary, this study recommends a proactive approach to addressing the environmental challenges posed by leather waste and proposes innovative solutions that optimize resource utilization and promote sustainable practices throughout the leather industry.

6. References

ADDIN CitaviBibliographyPublication bibliography

- Abbasi, Mohammad; Deymi–Dashtebayaz, Mahdi; Farzaneh–Gord, Mahmood; Abbasi, Sedigheh (2015): Assessment of a CHP system based on economical, fuel consumption and environmental considerations. In *International Journal of Global Warming* 7 (2), pp. 256–269.
- Abraham, Juliana; Gea, Teresa; Sánchez, Antoni (2014): Substitution of chemical dehairing by proteases from solid-state fermentation of hair wastes. In *Journal of cleaner production* 74, pp. 191–198.
- Adriani, R. P.; Kristanto, G. A.; Pratama, M. A. (2020): Greenhouse gas emission estimations for Depok's (West Java, Indonesia) middle-class household water end-uses (1), p. 12042.
- Agustini, Caroline B.; Da Fontoura, Juliana T.; Mella, Bianca; Gutterres, Mariliz (2018): Evaluating co-substrates to supplement biogas production from tannery solid waste treatment–cattle hair, microalgae biomass, and silicone. In *Biofuels, Bioproducts and Biorefining* 12 (6), pp. 1095–1102.
- Alamsyah, Rizal; Loebis, Enny Hawani (2014): Design and technical testing for crude biodiesel reactor using dry methods: Comparison of energy analysis. In *Energy Procedia* 47, pp. 235–241.
- Alengebawy, Ahmed; Mohamed, Badr A.; Ghimire, Nirmal; Jin, Keda; Liu, Tingting; Samer, Mohamed; Ai, Ping (2022): Understanding the environmental impacts of biogas utilization for energy production through life cycle assessment: An action towards reducing emissions. In *Environmental Research* 213, p. 113632.
- Alipal, J.; Pu'Ad, N. MohdA.S.; Lee, T. C.; Nayan, N. H.M.; Sahari, N.; Basri, H. et al. (2021): A review of gelatin: Properties, sources, process, applications, and commercialisation. In *Materials Today: Proceedings* 42, pp. 240–250.
- AlQattan, Nael; Acheampong, Michael; Jaward, Foday M.; Ertem, Funda Cansu; Vijayakumar, Nisha; Bello, Tolulope (2018): Reviewing the potential of Waste-to-Energy (WTE) technologies for Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) numbers seven and eleven. In *Renewable Energy Focus* 27, pp. 97–110.
- Alvarez, Rene; Liden, Gunnar (2008): Semi-continuous co-digestion of solid slaughterhouse waste, manure, and fruit and vegetable waste. In *Renewable Energy* 33 (4), pp. 726–734.
- Amdouni, Sana; Trabelsi, Aïda Ben Hassen; Elasmî, Amina Mabrouk; Chaghtmi, Raouia; Haddad, Khoulood; Jamaaoui, Faycel et al. (2021a): Tannery fleshing wastes conversion into high value-added biofuels and biochars using pyrolysis process. In *Fuel* 294, p. 120423.
- Amdouni, Sana; Trabelsi, Aïda Ben Hassen; Elasmî, Amina Mabrouk; Chaghtmi, Raouia; Haddad, Khoulood; Jamaaoui, Faycel et al. (2021b): Tannery fleshing wastes conversion into high value-added biofuels and biochars using pyrolysis process. In *Fuel* 294, p. 120423.
- Aragon-Briceño, Christian; Požarlik, Artur; Bramer, Eddy; Brem, Gerrit; Wang, Shule; Wen, Yuming et al. (2022): Integration of hydrothermal carbonization treatment for water and energy recovery from organic fraction of municipal solid waste digestate. In *Renewable Energy* 184, pp. 577–591.
- Arendt, Rosalie; Bach, Vanessa; Finkbeiner, Matthias (2021): Carbon offsets: an LCA perspective. In *Progress in Life Cycle Assessment 2019*, pp. 189–212.
- Barrena, Raquel; La Pagans, Estel; Artola, Adriana; Vázquez, Felicitas; Sánchez, Antoni (2007a): Co-composting of hair waste from the tanning industry with de-inking and municipal wastewater sludges. In *Biodegradation* 18, pp. 257–268.
- Barrena, Raquel; Pagans, Estel-la; Vázquez, Felicitas; Artola, Adriana; Sánchez, Antoni (2007b): Full-Scale Cocomposting of Hair Wastes from the Leather Manufacturing Industry and Sewage Sludge. In *Compost Science & Utilization* 15 (1), pp. 16–21. DOI: 10.1080/1065657X.2007.10702305.
- Belal Hossain, Md Abul Hashem; Sazzad, Sakil; Sahen, Md Sahariar (2023): COMPOSTING OF LEATHER SHAVING DUST: WASTE TO WEALTH APPROACH IN TANNERY.
- Bernstad, Anna; La Cour Jansen, Jes (2012): Review of comparative LCAs of food waste management systems–current status and potential improvements. In *Waste management* 32 (12), pp. 2439–2455.
- Bhagwat, Shivani; Ratnaparkhe, Supriya; Kumar, Anil (2015): Biomass pre-treatment methods and their economic viability for efficient production of biofuel. In *Br Biotechnol J* 8 (2), pp. 1–17.
- Bianco, Isabella; Panepinto, Deborah; Zanetti, Mariachiara (2021a): Environmental impacts of electricity from incineration and gasification: How the LCA approach can affect the results. In *Sustainability* 14 (1), p. 92.
- Bianco, Isabella; Panepinto, Deborah; Zanetti, Mariachiara (2021b): Environmental impacts of electricity from incineration and gasification: How the LCA approach can affect the results. In *Sustainability* 14 (1), p. 92.

- Bisinella, Valentina; Hulgaard, Tore; Riber, Christian; Damgaard, Anders; Christensen, Thomas H. (2021): Environmental assessment of carbon capture and storage (CCS) as a post-treatment technology in waste incineration. In *Waste management* 128, pp. 99–113.
- Boldrin, Alessio; Christensen, Thomas Højlund; Körner, Ina; Krogmann, Uta (2011): Composting: mass balances and product quality. In : *Solid Waste Technology and Management*: Wiley, pp. 569–582.
- Buljan, Jakov (2017): Leather Carbon Footprint Review of the European Standard EN 16887:2017. Leather - Environmental footprint - Product Category Rules (PCR), checked on 2017.
- Buljan, Jakov; Reich, Gunther; Ludvik, J. (2000): Mass balance in leather processing. In *the United Nations Industrial Development Organization. Regional Programme for Pollution Control in the Tanning Industry in South-East Asia*.
- Catalán, Eva; Komilis, Dimitrios; Sánchez, Antoni (2017a): Solid-state fermentation and composting as alternatives to treat hair waste: A life-cycle assessment comparative approach. In *Waste Management & Research* 35 (7), pp. 786–790.
- Catalán, Eva; Komilis, Dimitrios; Sánchez, Antoni (2017b): Solid-state fermentation and composting as alternatives to treat hair waste: A life-cycle assessment comparative approach. In *Waste Management & Research* 35 (7), pp. 786–790.
- CEA (2023): Power Sector at a Glance ALL INDIA _ Government of India _ Ministry of Power, June, 2023. Central Electricity Authority (CEA). Available online at <https://web.archive.org/web/20211104073555/https://powermin.gov.in/en/content/power-sector-glance-all-india>.
- Change, IPOC (2006): 2006 IPCC guidelines for national greenhouse gas inventories. In *Institute for global environmental strategies, Hayama, Kanagawa, Japan*.
- Chen, Wan-Ting; Zhang, Yuanhui; Zhang, Jixiang; Schideman, Lance; Yu, Guo; Zhang, Peng; Minarick, Mitchell (2014): Co-liquefaction of swine manure and mixed-culture algal biomass from a wastewater treatment system to produce bio-crude oil. In *Applied Energy* 128, pp. 209–268.
- Chojnacka, Katarzyna; Skrzypczak, Dawid; Mikula, Katarzyna; Witek-Krowiak, Anna; Izydorczyk, Grzegorz; Kuligowski, Ksawery et al. (2021): Progress in sustainable technologies of leather wastes valorization as solutions for the circular economy. In *Journal of cleaner production* 313, p. 127902.
- Colley, Tracey A.; Birkved, Morten; Olsen, Stig I.; Hauschild, Michael Z. (2020): Using a gate-to-gate LCA to apply circular economy principles to a food processing SME. In *Journal of cleaner production* 251, p. 119566.
- Colón, Joan; Cadena, Erasmo; Pognani, Michele; Barrena, Raquel; Sánchez, Antoni; Font, Xavier; Artola, Adriana (2012): Determination of the energy and environmental burdens associated with the biological treatment of source-separated municipal solid wastes. In *Energy & Environmental Science* 5 (2), pp. 5731–5741.
- CSE (2023): Methane Emissions From Open Dumpsites in India. Centre for Science and Environment.
- Da Souza, Franck Rosa de; Benvenuti, Jaqueline; Meyer, Michael; Wulf, Hauke; Klüver, Enno; Gutterres, Mariliz (2022a): Extraction of keratin from unhairing of bovine hide. In *Chemical Engineering Communications* 209 (1), pp. 118–126.
- Da Souza, Franck Rosa de; Benvenuti, Jaqueline; Meyer, Michael; Wulf, Hauke; Klüver, Enno; Gutterres, Mariliz (2022b): Extraction of keratin from unhairing of bovine hide. In *Chemical Engineering Communications* 209 (1), pp. 118–126.
- Dufour, Javier; Iribarren, Diego (2012): Life cycle assessment of biodiesel production from free fatty acid-rich wastes. In *Renewable Energy* 38 (1), pp. 155–162.
- Erasmo Cadena; Joan Colón; Adriana Artola; Antoni Sánchez; Xavier Font (2009): Environmental impact of two aerobic composting technologies using life cycle assessment. In *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 14, pp. 401–410. Available online at <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:4796370>.
- Etxabide, Alaitz; Leceta, Itsaso; Cabezudo, Sara; Guerrero, Pedro; La Caba, Koro de (2016): Sustainable fish gelatin films: From food processing waste to compost. In *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 4 (9), pp. 4626–4634.
- Famielec, Stanisław; Wieczorek-Ciurowa, Krystyna (2013): Incineration of tannery waste in a tunnel furnace system. In *Civil and Environmental Engineering Reports*.
- Fantozzi, Francesco; Bartocci, Pietro (2016): Carbon footprint as a tool to limit greenhouse gas emissions. In *Greenhouse Gases* 285.
- Fela, Katarzyna; Wieczorek-Ciurowa, Krystyna; Konopka, Michał; Woźny, Zenon (2011): Present and prospective leather industry waste disposal. In *Polish Journal of Chemical Technology* 13 (3), pp. 53–55.

- Feng, RuiZhe; Zaidi, Asad A.; Zhang, Kun; Shi, Yue (2019): Optimisation of microwave pretreatment for biogas enhancement through anaerobic digestion of microalgal biomass. In *Periodica Polytechnica Chemical Engineering* 63 (1), pp. 65–72.
- Feo, Giovanni de; Malvano, Carmela (2009): The use of LCA in selecting the best MSW management system. In *Waste management* 29 (6), pp. 1901–1915.
- Flores Tapia, Nelly Esther; Brito Moina, Hannibal (2023): Exploring Tannery Solid Wastes as a Source of Animal Feed. In *Processes* 11 (10), p. 2965.
- Forster, Piers M.; Smith, Chris; Walsh, Tristram; Lamb, William F.; Lamboll, Robin; Hall, Bradley et al. (2024): Indicators of Global Climate Change 2023: annual update of key indicators of the state of the climate system and human influence. In *Earth System Science Data* 16 (6), pp. 2625–2658.
- Frost, P.; Gilkinson, S. (2010): First 18 month performance summary for anaerobic digestion of dairy cow slurry at afbi hillsborough. In *Hillsborough: AgriFood Bioresour Inst (AFBI)*, pp. 1–12.
- Gahane, Dipali; Biswal, Divyajyoti; Mandavgane, Sachin A. (2022): Life cycle assessment of biomass pyrolysis. In *BioEnergy Research* 15 (3), pp. 1387–1406.
- Gallegos, J. PantojaL; Vergara, N. Dominguez; Perez, D. DominguezN (2022): Calculation of the fuel consumption, fuel economy and carbon dioxide emissions of a heavy-duty vehicle. In J. L.P. Gallegos, N. D. Vergara, D. N.D. Perez (Eds.): *Journal of Physics: Conference Series: IOP Publishing* (2307), p. 12025.
- Garg, Anushka; Basu, Soumen; Shetti, Nagaraj P.; Bhattu, Monika; Alodhayb, Abdullah; Pandiaraj, Saravanan (2024): Biowaste to bioenergy nexus: Fostering sustainability and circular economy. In *Environmental Research*, p. 118503.
- Gomes, Carolina Scaraffuni; Repke, Jens-Uwe; Meyer, Michael (2019): Diauxie during biogas production from collagen-based substrates. In *Renewable Energy* 141, pp. 20–27.
- Gomes, Carolina Scaraffuni; Repke, Jens-Uwe; Meyer, Michael (2020): Investigation of different pre-treatments of chromium leather shavings to improve biogas production. In *Journal of Leather Science and Engineering* 2, pp. 1–14.
- Gonawala, Suhas S.; Jardosh, Hemali (2018): Organic Waste in Composting: A brief review. In *IJCET* 8 (01). DOI: 10.14741/ijcet.v8i01.10884.
- Grippi, Donatella; Clemente, Rafael; Bernal, M. Pilar (2020): Chemical and bioenergetic characterization of biofuels from plant biomass: Perspectives for southern europe. In *Applied Sciences* 10 (10), p. 3571.
- Gupta, Amit K.; Sinha, Sarita (2006): Chemical fractionation and heavy metal accumulation in the plant of *Sesamum indicum* (L.) var. T55 grown on soil amended with tannery sludge: Selection of single extractants. In *Chemosphere* 64 (1), pp. 161–173.
- Hashem, Md Abul; Paul, Hridoy; Akash, Md Sabbir Rahman; Mim, Sadia; Zahin, Md Enamul Hasan (2024a): Atypical co-composting technique of managing tannery limed fleshing. In *Waste Management Bulletin* 1 (4), pp. 23–29.
- Hashem, Md Abul; Paul, Hridoy; Akash, Md Sabbir Rahman; Mim, Sadia; Zahin, Md Enamul Hasan (2024b): Atypical co-composting technique of managing tannery limed fleshing. In *Waste Management Bulletin* 1 (4), pp. 23–29.
- Heng, Lijun; Zhang, Huiyan; Xiao, Jun; Xiao, Rui (2018): Life cycle assessment of polyol fuel from corn stover via fast pyrolysis and upgrading. In *ACS Sustainable Chemistry & Engineering* 6 (2), pp. 2733–2740.
- Hossain, Md Refat; Islam, Mahamud-UI; Islam, Shajneen; Haque, Md Morshedul; Fatema, Ummul Khair (2024): Valorization of textile sludge and tannery fleshing wastes through co-hydrous pyrolysis within the domain of biocrude production. In *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, pp. 1–14.
- IPCC (2014): Mitigation of climate change. In *Contribution of working group III to the fifth assessment report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change* 1454, p. 147.
- ISO (1998): Environmental Management: Life Cycle Assessment: Goal and Scope Definition and Inventory Analysis: ISO 14041: International Organization for Standardization.
- ISO, I. (2006): Environmental Management–Life Cycle Assessment–Requirement and Guidelines. In S. (2006b). ISO 14044.
- ISO, I. S.O. (2000): 14043: Environmental management–life cycle assessment–life cycle interpretation. In *EN ISO 14043*, p. 18.
- Jahirul, Mohammad I.; Rasul, Mohammad G.; Chowdhury, Ashfaque Ahmed; Ashwath, Nanjappa (2012): Biofuels production through biomass pyrolysis—a technological review. In *Energies* 5 (12), pp. 4952–5001.

- Jeswani, Harish K.; Smith, Rachele W.; Azapagic, Adisa (2013): Energy from waste: carbon footprint of incineration and landfill biogas in the UK. In *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 18, pp. 218–229.
- Kiliç, Eylem; Puig Vidal, Rita; Baquero Armans, Grau; Zengin, Gökhan (2014): Carbon footprint and energy balance of biodiesel produced from tannery fleshings.
- Kılıç, Eylem; Puig, Rita; Baquero, Grau; Zengin, Gökhan; Zengin, Arife Candaş Adıgüzel (2013): Carbon footprint and energy comparison of biodiesel produced from leather industry fleshings and rapeseed vegetable oil, pp. 320–327.
- Kluska, Jacek; Ochnio, Mateusz; Kardaś, Dariusz; Heda, Łukasz (2019): The influence of temperature on the physicochemical properties of products of pyrolysis of leather-tannery waste. In *Waste management* 88, pp. 248–256.
- Komilis, Dimitris P.; Ham, Robert K. (2004): Life-cycle inventory of municipal solid waste and yard waste windrow composting in the United States. In *Journal of environmental engineering* 130 (11), pp. 1390–1400.
- Kubendran, Devaraj; Salma Aathika, Abdur Rawoof; Amudha, Thanarasu; Thiruselvi, Devaraj; Yuvarani, Mani; Sivanesan, Subramanian (2017): Utilization of leather fleshing waste as a feedstock for sustainable biodiesel production. In *Energy Sources, Part A: Recovery, Utilization, and Environmental Effects* 39 (15), pp. 1587–1593. DOI: 10.1080/15567036.2017.1349218.
- Lakhout, Abderrahim; Alsulami, Badr T. (2020): Evaluation of risk assessment of landfill emissions and their impacts on human health. In *Arabian Journal of Geosciences* 13 (22), p. 1185.
- Liu, Yili; Sun, Weixin; Liu, Jianguo (2017): Greenhouse gas emissions from different municipal solid waste management scenarios in China: Based on carbon and energy flow analysis. In *Waste management* 68, pp. 653–661.
- Maalouf, Amani; El-Fadel, Mutasem (2019): Life cycle assessment for solid waste management in Lebanon: Economic implications of carbon credit. In *Waste Management & Research* 37 (1_suppl), pp. 14–26.
- Malakahmad, Amirhossein; Abualqumboz, Motasem S.; Kutty, Shamsul Rahman M.; Abunama, Taher J. (2017): Assessment of carbon footprint emissions and environmental concerns of solid waste treatment and disposal techniques; case study of Malaysia. In *Waste management* 70, pp. 282–292.
- Masilamani, Dineshkumar; Ariram, Naisini; Madhan, Balaraman; Palanivel, Saravanan (2023): An integrated process for effective utilization of collagenous protein from raw hide trimmings: Valorization of tannery solid wastes. In *Journal of cleaner production* 415, p. 137705.
- Masilamani, Dineshkumar; Madhan, Balaraman; Shanmugam, Ganesh; Palanivel, Saravanan; Narayan, Bhaskar (2016): Extraction of collagen from raw trimming wastes of tannery: a waste to wealth approach. In *Journal of cleaner production* 113, pp. 338–344.
- Maurer, Claudia; Müller, Joachim (2019): Drying characteristics of biogas digestate in a hybrid waste-heat/solar dryer. In *Energies* 12 (7), p. 1294.
- McDougall, Forbes R.; White, Peter R.; Franke, Marina; Hindle, Peter (2008): Integrated solid waste management: a life cycle inventory: John Wiley & Sons.
- Menikpura, Nirmala; Premakumara, Jagath Dickella Gamaralalage (2021): User Manual for Estimation Tool for Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions from Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) Management in a Life Cycle Perspective. Available online at <https://www.iges.or.jp/en/pub/user-manual-estimation-tool-ghg-emissions-mswm-china/en>.
- Mezzullo, William G.; McManus, Marcelle C.; Hammond, Geoff P. (2013): Life cycle assessment of a small-scale anaerobic digestion plant from cattle waste. In *Applied Energy* 102, pp. 657–664.
- Moghadam, Reza; Suzana, Yusup; Ghani, Wan; Nehzati, Shahab; Tavasoli, Ahmad (2014): Investigation on syngas production via biomass conversion through the integration of pyrolysis and air–steam gasification processes. In *Energy Conversion and Management* 87, pp. 670–675. DOI: 10.1016/j.enconman.2014.07.065.
- Mohammadi, A.; Venkatesh, G.; Sandberg, M.; Eskandari, S.; Granström, K. (2019): Life cycle assessment of combination of anaerobic digestion and pyrolysis: focusing on different options for biogas use. *Adv Geosci* 49: 57–66.
- Moktadir, Md Abdul; Ahmadi, Hadi Badri; Sultana, Razia; Liou, James J. H.; Rezaei, Jafar (2020): Circular economy practices in the leather industry: A practical step towards sustainable development. In *Journal of cleaner production* 251, p. 119737.
- Moktadir, Md Abdul; Rahman, Mohammed Mizanur (2022): Energy production from leather solid wastes by anaerobic digestion: A critical review. In *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews* 161, p. 112378.

- Mondal, Sumonta Kumar; Hossain, Md Tofazzul; Hashem, Md Abul; Haque, Md Sanaul (2022): LEATHER BUFFING DUST IN COMPOSITE FABRICATION: SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN TANNERY.
- Mozhiarasi, Velusamy; Natarajan, Thillai Sivakumar; Karthik, Vijayarangan; Anburajan, Parthiban (2023): Potential of biofuel production from leather solid wastes: Indian scenario. In *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 30 (60), pp. 125214–125237.
- Muthu, Subramanian Senthilkannan (2014): Assessment of Carbon Footprint in Different Industrial Sectors, Volume 2: Springer.
- Noushabadi, Abolfazl Sajadi; Dashti, Amir; Ahmadijokani, Farhad; Hu, Jinguang; Mohammadi, Amir H. (2021): Estimation of higher heating values (HHVs) of biomass fuels based on ultimate analysis using machine learning techniques and improved equation. In *Renewable Energy* 179, pp. 550–562.
- Oliveira, Mariana; Zucaro, Amalia; Passaro, Renato; Ulgiati, Sergio (2024): Life cycle assessment of leather treatment at various scales: comparison between chrome and vegetable processes. In *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 29 (2), pp. 153–173.
- Onur Yılmaz; I. Cem Kantarli; Mithat Yuksel; Mehmet Saglam; Jale Yanik (2007): Conversion of leather wastes to useful products. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 49 (4), pp. 436–448. DOI: 10.1016/j.resconrec.2006.05.006.
- Onyuka, Arthur (2010): Sustainable management of tannery hair waste through composting: University of Northampton.
- Onyuka, Arthur; Bates, Margaret P.; Attenburrow, Geoff E.; Covington, Anthony D.; Antunes, A. Paula M. (2012): Parameters for composting tannery hair waste. In *Journal of the American Leather Chemists Association* 107 (5), pp. 159–166.
- Oviedo-Ocaña, Edgar Ricardo; Abendroth, Christian; Domínguez, I. C.; Sánchez, Antoni; Dornack, Christina (2023): Life cycle assessment of biowaste and green waste composting systems: A review of applications and implementation challenges. In *Waste management* 171, pp. 350–364.
- Ozgunay, Hasan; Colak, S.; Mutlu, M. M.; Akyuz, F. (2007): Characterization of Leather Industry Wastes. In *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies* 16 (6).
- Parvin, Shamima; Mazumder, Lubana Tasnim; Hasan, Shahnoor; Rabbani, Khondkar Ayaz; Rahman, Mohammad Lutfor (2017): What should we do with our solid tannery waste. In *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology* 11 (4), pp. 82–89.
- Pérez, Javier; Andrés, Juan Manuel de; Lumbreras, Julio; Rodríguez, Encarnación (2018): Evaluating carbon footprint of municipal solid waste treatment: Methodological proposal and application to a case study. In *Journal of cleaner production* 205, pp. 419–431.
- Peters, Greg; Li, Mengyu; Lenzen, Manfred (2021): The need to decelerate fast fashion in a hot climate-A global sustainability perspective on the garment industry. In *Journal of cleaner production* 295, p. 126390.
- POPIȚA, Gabriela-Emilia; MANCIULA, Dorin; POPOVICI, Antoanela; Cristina, ROȘU (2020): CONDUCTOMETRIC TESTS AND TOTAL CHROMIUM LEACHABILITY IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION, FROM TANNED LEATHER WASTE. In *Studia Universitatis Babeș-Bolyai Ambientum*, pp. 59–73.
- Pwc India, 2023: fuelling-indias-future-with-bioenergy. Available online at <https://www.pwc.in/research-and-insights-hub/fuelling-indias-future-with-bioenergy.html>, checked on 01.2023.
- Quina, Margarida J.; Bordado, João C. M.; Quinta-Ferreira, Rosa M. (2011): Air pollution control in municipal solid waste incinerators. In *The impact of air pollution on health, economy, environment and agricultural sources* 1, pp. 331–358.
- Rajmohan, K. S.; Ramya, C.; Varjani, Sunita (2021): Trends and advances in bioenergy production and sustainable solid waste management. In *Energy & Environment* 32 (6), pp. 1059–1085.
- Ramya, Kadathur Ramachandran; Sathish, Murali; Madhan, Balaraman; Jaisankar, Sellamuthu Nagappan; Saravanan, Palanivel (2022): Effective utilization of tannery hair waste to develop a high-performing re-tanning agent for cleaner leather manufacturing. In *Journal of Environmental Management* 302, p. 114029.
- Ramya, Kadathur Ramachandran; Thangam, Ramar; Madhan, Balaraman (2020): Comparative analysis of the chemical treatments used in keratin extraction from red sheep's hair and the cell viability evaluations of this keratin for tissue engineering applications. In *Process Biochemistry* 90, pp. 223–232.
- Ravindranath, E.; Kalyanaraman, Chitra; Begum, S. Shamshath; Gopalakrishnan, A. Navaneetha (2010): Effect of recirculation rate on anaerobic treatment of fleshing using UASB reactor with recovery of energy. In *0975-1084*.
- Rinke Dias de Souza, Nariê; Colling Klein, Bruno; Ferreira Chagas, Mateus; Cavalett, Otavio; Bonomi, Antonio (2021): Towards comparable carbon credits: harmonization of LCA models of cellulosic biofuels. In *Sustainability* 13 (18), p. 10371.

- Sampaio, Ana Paula C.; Sá M Sousa Filho, Men de; Castro, Ana Lídia A.; Figueirêdo, Maria Cléa B. de (2017): Life cycle assessment from early development stages: the case of gelatin extracted from tilapia residues. In *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 22, pp. 767–783.
- Sandhya, K. V.; Abinandan, Sudharsanam; Vedaraman, N.; Velappan, K. C. (2016): Extraction of fleshing oil from waste limed fleshings and biodiesel production. In *Waste management* 48, pp. 638–643.
- Saranya, G.; Ramachandra, T. V. (2020): Life cycle assessment of biodiesel from estuarine microalgae. In *Energy Conversion and Management: X* 8, p. 100065.
- Scharff, Heijo; Jacobs, Joeri (2006): Applying guidance for methane emission estimation for landfills. In *Waste management* 26 (4), pp. 417–429.
- Scharff, Heijo; Kok, B.; Krom, A. H. (2007): The role of sustainable landfill in future waste management systems, pp. 1–8.
- Sebastian, Mihai (2014): Industrial gelatin manufacture—theory and practice.
- Senthil, Rethinam; Hemalatha, Thiagarajan; Manikandan, Ramasamy; Das, Bhabendra Nath; Sastry, Thotapalli Parvathaleswara (2015): Leather boards from buffing dust: a novel perspective. In *Clean Techn Environ Policy* 17 (2), pp. 571–576. DOI: 10.1007/s10098-014-0831-7.
- Senthil, Rethinam; Kavukcu, Serdar Batıkan; Çakır, Sinem; Türkmen, Hayati; Başaran, Bahri; Alagumuthu, Tamilselvi (2022): Utilization of various solid leather wastes for the production of blended bricks. In *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy* 24 (6), pp. 1889–1901.
- Senthil, Rethinam; Kavukcu, Serdar Batıkan; Sinem, Çakır; Tunçay, Karaer Aslihan (2023a): Efficacy of natural polymer leather sheet with papermill sludge and leather waste: a novel recycling perspective. In *Clean Technologies and Environmental Policy* 25 (9), pp. 2889–2901.
- Senthil, Rethinam; Kavukcu, Serdar Batıkan; Sinem, Çakır; Tunçay, Karaer Aslihan (2023b): Efficacy of natural polymer leather sheet with papermill sludge and leather waste: a novel recycling perspective. In *Clean Techn Environ Policy* 25 (9), pp. 2889–2901.
- Shakil, Md Saidur Rahman; Ahmed, Sobur; Pathan, Estehad (2019): Tannery solid waste into wealth by non-edible gelatin production from raw trimmings. In *European Journal of Engineering and Technology Research* 4 (10), pp. 167–172.
- Siddiqua, Ayesha; Hahladakis, John N.; Al-Attiya, Wadha Ahmed KA (2022): An overview of the environmental pollution and health effects associated with waste landfilling and open dumping. In *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 29 (39), pp. 58514–58536.
- Slorach, Peter C.; Jeswani, Harish K.; Cuéllar-Franca, Rosa; Azapagic, Adisa (2019): Energy demand and carbon footprint of treating household food waste compared to its prevention. In *Energy Procedia* 161, pp. 17–23.
- Sousa, Vitor M. Z.; Luz, Sandra M.; Caldeira-Pires, Armando; Machado, Frederico S.; Silveira, Cristiano M. (2017): Life cycle assessment of biodiesel production from beef tallow in Brazil. In *The International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 22, pp. 1837–1850.
- Sri Bala Kameswari, Kanchinadham; Kalyanaraman, Chitra; Porselvam, Subramanian; Thanasekaran, Kumarasami (2011): Enhancement of Biogas Generation by Addition of Lipase in the Co-Digestion of Tannery Solid Wastes. In *CLEAN—Soil, Air, Water* 39 (8), pp. 781–786.
- Stavins, Robert N. (1997): Policy instruments for climate change: how can national governments address a global problem. In *U. Chi. Legal F.*, p. 293.
- Subramaniam, Vijaya; Choo, Y. M. (2012): Greenhouse gas emissions for the production of crude palm kernel oil - A gate-to-gate case study. In *Journal of oil palm research* 24, pp. 1511–1517.
- Technical Committee ISO/TC 207, Environmental Management (2006): Environmental management-life cycle assessment-principles and framework: International Organization for Standardization.
- Thannimalay, Letchumi (2013): Life Cycle Assessment of Sodium Hydroxide. In *Australian Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*.
- UNIDO (2010): Future trends in the world leather and leather products industry and trade: United Nations Industrial Development Organization Vienna.
- United Nations (2019): The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2019: United Nations New York, NY, USA.
- Velusamy, Mozhiarasi; Chakali, Bhagiratha; Ganesan, Sathish; Tinwala, Farha; Shanmugham Venkatachalam, Srinivasan (2020): Investigation on pyrolysis and incineration of chrome-tanned solid waste from tanneries for effective treatment and disposal: an experimental study. In *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 27, pp. 29778–29790.

- Vigneswaran, S.; Kandasamy, J.; Johir, M.A.H. (2016): Sustainable Operation of Composting in Solid Waste Management. In *Procedia Environmental Sciences* 35, pp. 408–415. DOI: 10.1016/j.proenv.2016.07.022.
- Wang, Hui; Wang, Lijun; Shahbazi, Abolghasem (2015a): Life cycle assessment of fast pyrolysis of municipal solid waste in North Carolina of USA. In *Journal of cleaner production* 87, pp. 511–519.
- Wang, Hui; Wang, Lijun; Shahbazi, Abolghasem (2015b): Life cycle assessment of fast pyrolysis of municipal solid waste in North Carolina of USA. In *Journal of cleaner production* 87, pp. 511–519.
- Wang, Junqi; Okopi, Solomon Inalegwu; Ma, Haoxiang; Wang, Miao; Chen, Rui; Tian, Wangyang; Xu, Fuqing (2021): Life cycle assessment of the integration of anaerobic digestion and pyrolysis for treatment of municipal solid waste. In *Bioresource Technology* 338, p. 125486.
- Watch, Climate (2022): Climate watch: Tech. rep, World Resources Institute, Washington, DC, 2020, URL [https://www ...](https://www...)
- White, P.; Franke, M.; Hindle, P. (1995): Lifecycle inventory: a part of lifecycle assessment. In *Integrated Solid Waste Management: A Lifecycle Inventory*, pp. 25–36.
- Xavier, Cristiane an; Moset, Verónica; Wahid, Radziah; Møller, Henrik B. (2015): The efficiency of shredded and briquetted wheat straw in anaerobic co-digestion with dairy cattle manure. In *Biosystems Engineering* 139, pp. 16–24.
- Yadav, Pooja; Samadder, Sukha Ranjan (2018): Environmental impact assessment of municipal solid waste management options using life cycle assessment: a case study. In *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 25, pp. 838–854.
- Yao, Lin Peng; Zeng, Qi; Qi, Ting; Li, Jia (2020): An environmentally friendly discharge technology to pretreat spent lithium-ion batteries. In *Journal of cleaner production* 245, p. 118820.
- Yap, Chi Nam; Hadibarata, Tony (2022): REMEDIATION OF CONTAMINATED SOIL WITH CRUDE OIL BY COMPOSTING. In *Journal of Civil Engineering, Science and Technology* 13 (1), pp. 49–58.
- Yazid, Noraziah Abu; Barrera, Raquel; Sánchez, Antoni (2016): Assessment of protease activity in hydrolysed extracts from SSF of hair waste by and indigenous consortium of microorganisms. In *Waste management* 49, pp. 420–426.
- Yentekakis, Ioannis V.; Goula, Grammatiki (2017): Biogas management: advanced utilization for production of renewable energy and added-value chemicals. In *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 5, p. 7.
- Yılmaz, Onur; Kantarli, I. Cem; Yuksel, Mithat; Saglam, Mehmet; Yanik, Jale (2007a): Conversion of leather wastes to useful products. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 49 (4), pp. 436–448.
- Yılmaz, Onur; Kantarli, I. Cem; Yuksel, Mithat; Saglam, Mehmet; Yanik, Jale (2007b): Conversion of leather wastes to useful products. In *Resources, Conservation and Recycling* 49 (4), pp. 436–448.
- Zaman, Atiq Uz (2013): Life cycle assessment of pyrolysis–gasification as an emerging municipal solid waste treatment technology. In *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 10, pp. 1029–1038.
- Zaman, Chowdhury Zaira; Pal, Kaushik; Yehye, Wageeh A.; Sagadevan, Suresh; Shah, Syed Tawab; Adebisi, Ganiyu Abimbola et al. (2017): Pyrolysis: a sustainable way to generate energy from waste. In *Pyrolysis* 1, pp. 3–36.
- Zimmer, Tobias; Rudi, Andreas; Glöser-Chahoud, Simon; Schultmann, Frank (2022): Techno-economic analysis of intermediate pyrolysis with solar drying: a chilean case study. In *Energies* 15 (6), p. 2272.

Appendix

I. Auxiliary materials

Table 36. Total carbon footprint for different auxiliary materials

S.No.	Materials (kg)	CO ₂ eqq/kg	References
1	NH ₃	2.4	iea.org
2	NO ₂	296	(Subramaniam and Choo 2012)
3	Water	0.379	(Adriani et al. 2020)
4	Diesel	2.6	(Gallegos et al. 2022)
5	NaOH	0.6329	(Thannimalay 2013)
6	NaCl	0.06	carboncloud.com
7	Na ₂ CO ₃	0.46	carboncloud.com
8	HCl	0.89	winipegg.ca
10	CaO	0.15	winipegg.ca
11	Na ₂ SO ₄	0.47	winipegg.ca
12	NH ₄ Cl	1.18	winipegg.ca
13	NH ₄ SO ₄	2.3	www.danfertilizers.com
14	Gelatin	18.55	carboncloud.com
15	Na ₂ SO ₃	0.47	carboncloud.com
16	Latex	0.13	carboncloud.com

II.
O

pen dumping emissions

To evaluate the decomposable degradable organic carbon (Menikpura and Premakumara 2021; Scharff and Jacobs 2006) :

$$DDOC_{(T)} = W_{(T)} * DOC * DOC_f * MCF$$

Here, $W_{(T)}$ is the amount of waste deposited in the current year, T is a period, DOC is degradable organic carbon under aerobic conditions, DOC_f is a fraction of DOC under anaerobic conditions, and MCF is the CH₄ correction factor. DOC will change with changes in the type of waste (Table 2),

Table 37. Calculation of carbon content in different leather waste

S.No.	Category	Carbon content (%)	Total solid (%)	Carbon content per ton of waste (kg)
1	Raw trimmings	40	37.5	150
2	Fleshings	40	20	80
3	Hair	50	89	445
4	Chrome shavings	43	82	352.6
5	Buffing dust	45	87.5	393.7
6	Crust trimmings	67.1	87	584
7	Finishing waste	67.1	87	584

III. Calculation of specific heat

Specific heat capacity has been calculated with the equation from (Chen et al. 2014; Hossain et al. 2024) and moisture loss with required heat from (Zimmer et al. 2022) .

$$ECR_{co-HTL} = \frac{(W_i * C_{pw} * T + (1 - W_i) * C_{pm} * T)(1 - Rh)}{Y * HHV * (1 - W_i) * R_c}$$

Here, ECR is net energy gain in the system: 1; Rh (efficiency of heat recovery) is 0.5; W_i is the initial moisture content: 62.5% for raw trimmings, 80% for fleshings, 18.35% for chrome, C_{pw} is the specific heat capacity of water: 4.18 kJ/kg.K, T is the difference between the designated reaction temperature and the initial temperature (assumed to be 25°C), Y is the bio-crude oil yield, HHV is the higher heating value of bio-crude oil.

A final % moisture content of 15% has been considered for utilization in the pyrolysis unit to maintain the moisture content as mentioned in inventories. The amount of heat is required (Zimmer et al. 2022; Maurer and Müller 2019),

$Q_{dry} \text{ (MJ)} = \text{Massflow(kg)} * \text{Specific heat capacity(KJ/kg}^{-1} \text{ k}^{-1} \text{)} * \text{Temperature difference in kelvin}$

IV. Calculation of Moisture removal

$$EWP = \frac{FLI * MC_{ini} - MC_{fin}}{1 - MC_{fin}}$$

Here, MC_{ini} and MC_{fin} are initial and final moisture contents of the digestate

V. Carbon footprint values (sanitary landfill from literature)

Table 38. The carbon footprint values (Buljan 2017) .

S.No.	Waste	CO₂kg-eq./ton (Buljan 2017)
1	Putrefied hides/skins	624
2	Raw trimmings	624
3	Hair (pasting)	373
4	Lime splits	624
5	Fleshing	624
6	Wet blue trimmings	221
7	Chrome splitting (bovine)	221
8	Chrome shavings	221
9	Crust shavings	221
10	Buffing dust	221
11	Dyed trimmings	221

The CF values for each waste followed by supervision can be 10 – 20 times higher under lack of proper supervision.

VI. Inventories

Table 39. Inventories data

S. No	Base Scenarios	Phase	Unit	Base_Quantity	Raw trimmings	Fleshings	Hair (Bovine)	Chrome shavings/splits	Buffing dust	Crust trimmings	Finishing waste	Refereneces
1	Anaerobic digestion with or without small pyrolysis unit (1 ton as FU, Fleshings with 0.455 m ³ /kg VS, Chrome shavings & splits with 0.375 m ³ /kg VS, Raw trimmings with 0.547 m ³ /kg VS)	Shredding	kWh/t	30-60 (45)	45.00	45.00	X	45.00	X	X	X	(Xavier et al. 2015)
		Transportation	km	20.00	20.00	20.00	X	20.00	X	X	X	Assumption
		Waste (1-Ton as FU)	kg	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	X	1000.00	X	X	X	Assumption
		Conveyor belt	kWh/t	3.00	3.00	3.00	X	3.00	X	X	X	(Yao et al. 2020)
		AD chamber (EC)	kWh/t	5.40	5.40	5.40	X	5.40	X	X	X	(Frost and Gilkinson 2010)
		Total solids	%	varies	37.50	20.00	X	82.00	X	X	X	Table 2
		Biogas conversion	%	60.00	60.00	60.00	X	60.00	X	X	X	(Khalid et al. 2011)
		Total volatile solids	%	varies	59.00	80.00	X	80.00	X	X	X	Table 2
		Biogas filtration with compressor (EC)	kWh/m ³	0.11	0.11	0.11	X	0.11	X	X	X	(Abbasi et al. 2015)
		Biogas purification water and H₂S removal	kWh/m ³	0.12	0.12	0.12	X	0.12	X	X	X	
		NaOH	kWh/m ³	0.04	0.04	0.04	X	0.04	X	X	X	
		Hydrogen sulfide	kWh/m ³	0.04	0.04	0.04	X	0.04	X	X	X	
		CHP unit (EC)	kWh/m ³	0.20	0.20	0.20	X	0.20	X	X	X	(Abbasi et al. 2015)
		Energy production	kWh/m ³	9.95	9.95	9.95	X	9.95	X	X	X	(Gioulounta et al. 2022)
		Heat production	MJ/m ³	17.64	17.64	17.64	X	17.64	X	X	X	(Cusenza et al. 2021)
		Heat Percentage	%	37.30	37.30	37.30	X	37.30	X	X	X	(Santoli et al. 2017)
		Energy percentage	%	51.50	51.50	51.50	X	51.50	X	X	X	(Santoli et al. 2017)
Lubricating oil	%	0.65	0.65	0.65	X	0.65	X	X	X	(Alengebawy et al. 2022)		
Dewatering (EC)	kWh/kg	0.05	0.05	0.05	X	0.05	X	X	X	(Mohammadi et al. 2019)		

		Conveyor belt	kWh/t	3.00	3.00	3.00	X	3.00	X	X	X	(Yao et al. 2020)
		Thermal drying (MJ)	MJ/total digestate (by formula)	varies	na	103.25	X	22.94	X	X	X	(Zimmer et al. 2022)
		Final moisture	%	15.00	na	15.00	X	15.00	X	X	X	(Zimmer et al. 2022)
		Current moisture	%	varies	na	80.00	X	18.00	X	X	X	
		Final Temp	°C	120.00	na	120.00	X	120.00	X	X	X	
		Current Temp	°C	35.00	na	35.00	X	35.00	X	X	X	Assumption
		Specific heat capacity	KJkg-1k-1	varies	na	3.48	X	0.80	X	X	X	(Hossain et al. 2024)
		Evaporated water	kg (by formula)	varies	na	61.18	X	3.15	X	X	X	(Zimmer et al. 2022)
		Pyrolysis unit	kWh/kg	varies	na	0.34	X	0.34	X	X	X	(Wang et al. 2015a; Wang et al. 2021) for energy consumption, (Amdouni et al. 2021b) at °C for fleshings, (Velusamy et al. 2020a) for chrome shavings, (Almeida et al. 2017) , for raw trimmings 600°C)
		Biochar	%	varies	na	0.37	X	30.00	X	X	X	
		Biooil	%	varies	na	0.60	X	49.00	X	X	X	
		Methane	%	varies	na	0.00	X	0.40	X	X	X	
		Emissions	%	varies	na	0.03	X	14.93	X	X	X	
		Carbon dioxide	%	varies	na	0.00	X	3.71	X	X	X	
Carbon monoxide	%	varies	na	0.00	X	1.96	X	X	X			
2	Composting (Turned windrow composting, Fleshings & static-pile composting for Hair waste)	Waste	kg	1000.00	X	1000.00	1000.00	X	X	X	X	Assumption
		Chicken excreta (fleshings)	kg	varies	X	227.80	0.00	X	X	X	X	In the case of fleshings (Belal Hossain, Md Abul Hashem et al. 2023)
		Cowpats (fleshings)	kg	varies	X	164.50	0.00	X	X	X	X	
		Sawdust (fleshings)	kg	varies	X	164.56	0.00	X	X	X	X	
		Wastewater (Hair)	kg	varies		0.00	1000.00	X	X	X	X	
		Pretreatment	kWh/kg	0.05	X	0.05	0.05	X	X	X	X	(Xavier et al. 2015)
		Pre and Pro-composting (trommel)	kWh/kg	0.00	X	0.00	0.00	X	X	X	X	(Komilis and Ham 2004)
			kWh/kg	0.00	X	0.00	0.00	X	X	X	X	
		Emissions			X			X	X	X	X	
CO ₂	kg/ton-waste	varies	X	0.12	0.03	X	X	X	X	(Boldrin et al. 2011) for fleshings, (Barrena et		

		Final compost	%	varies	X	77.00	57.8	X	X	X	X	al. 2007a) , for hair waste	
		Oxygen supply	kg	varies	X	0.24	0.00	X	X	X	X	(Boldrin et al. 2011)	
		Water required	kg	varies	X	0.21	0.21	X	X	X	X	(Boldrin et al. 2011)	
		Using a tool for GHG Emissions (Scharff et al. 2007)											
3	Open dumping for 1 ton as FU for any leather waste)	Waste	kg	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	1000.00	X	Assumption	
		Transportation	km	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	20.00	X	Assumption
		Pretreatment	kWh/kg	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.05	X	(Xavier et al. 2015)
		Conveyor belt	kWh/t	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	X	(Yao et al. 2020)
		Emissions											Considering the biodegradability (DOC) of pretanning waste as Garden waste; For post tanning waste it is considered equal to industrial waste (Change 2006; Menikpura and Premakumara 2021) .
		CO ₂	kg	varies	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		CH ₄	kg	varies	39.9	24	39.9	29.925	29.925	29.925	29.925	29.925	
		Carbon content	kg/ton	varies	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		DOC	%	varies	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	
		DOC _f	0.5	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	
		16/12 (CH ₄ /ton)	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	1.33	
		MCF		0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	
		C	Methane concentration (50%)	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50	
4	Pyrolysis	Waste	kg	1000	na	1000	na	1000	na	na	1000	Assumption	
		Transportation	km	20	na	20	na	20	na	na	20	Assumption	
		Pretreatment	kWh/kg	0.045	na	0.045	na	0.045	na	na	0.045	(Xavier et al. 2015)	
		Conveyor belt	kWh/t	3	na	3	na	3	na	na	3	(Yao et al. 2020)	
		Dewatering	kWh/kg	0.05	0.05	0.05	X	0.05	X	X	X	(Mohammadi et al. 2019)	
		Thermal drying										(Zimmer et al. 2022)	
		Specific heat cap	KJkg ⁻¹ k ⁻¹	varies	na	3.6	na	2.7429	na	na	0.80	04	(Hossain et al. 2024)

		Highest temp	°C	120	na	120	na	120	na	na	120	(Zimmer et al. 2022)
		Final moisture target	%	15	na	15	na	15	na	na	15	
		Pyrolysis unit	kWh/kg	0.336	na	0.336	na	0.336	na	na	0.336	(Wang, Wang et al. 2015, Wang, Okopi et al. 2021)
		Biochar	%	varies	na	0.3717	na	30	na	na	0.27	
		Bioil	%	varies	na	0.6	na	49	na	na	0.52	
		CH ₄	%	varies	na	0.00953	na	0.399	na	na	0.3969	
		CO ₂	%	varies	na	na	na	3.7128	na	na	6.4197	
		Remaining emissions	%	varies	na	0.01877	na	13.3539	na	na		
		CO	%	varies	na	9.89625	na	1.9551	na	na	1.4154	
		H ₂	%	varies	na	0.01711895	na	1.5792	na	na	0.8337	
		Cnhm	%	varies	na	0.01649375	na	0	na	na	0	
		Gas yield total	%	varies	na	0.25375	na	21	na	na	0.21	
		LHV (MJ/Nm3)	%	varies	na	7 to 10	na	15	na	na	19.9	
		Followed by CHP unit	Same as previous section									
5	Incineration	Waste	kg	1000	na	na	na	1000	na	na		
		Transportation	km	20	na	na	na	20	na	na		Assumption
		Feed hoper	kWh/kg	0.0066	na	na	na	0.0066	na	na		https://delukecrane.en.made-in-china.com/product/LdVAlmrbFRg/China-15t-Overhead-Grab-Crane-for-City-Waste-Incineration-Plant.html
		Moving grate	kWh/kg	0.0085	na	na	na	0.0085	na	na		https://vecoplan.com/en/products/conveying/belt-conveyor/vfb-conveyor-belt
		Furnace	kWh/kg		na	na	na	0.1	na	na		(Thomson et al. 2000)
		Activated carbon	kWh/kg	0.0021	na	na	na	0.0021	na	na		(Bianco et al. 2021)
		Bottom ash	%	0.219	na	na	na	0.219	na	na		
		Diesel	%	0.000084	na	na	na	0.000084	na	na		
		Fan	kWh/kg	0.004	na	na	na	0.004	na	na		
		Lime	%	0	na	na	na	0	na	na		

		Limestone	%	0	na	na	na	0	na	na		
		Sodium carbonate	%	0.0178	na	na	na	0.0178	na	na		
		Urea	%	0.003	na	na	na	0.003	na	na		
		Blast furnace slag	%	0	na	na	na	0	na	na		
		Boiler			na	na	na		na	na		
		Heat production	kWh/kg	550	na	na	na	550	na	na		
		Fabric filter baghouse	kWh/kg	0.004	na	na	na	0.004	na	na		https://www.riedel-filtertechnik.com/en/competences-products/exhaust-air-cleaning/fabric-filter
		Emissions			na	na	na		na	na		
		APC residues	%	0.0147	na	na	na	0.0147	na	na		(Bianco et al. 2021)
		Ammonia	%	0.00003075	na	na	na	0.00003075	na	na		
		CO ₂ biogenic	%	0.5775	na	na	na	0.5775	na	na		
		CO ₂ fossil	%	0.3507	na	na	na	0.3507	na	na		
		Fan	kWh/kg	0.004	na	na	na	0.004	na	na		
		N ₂ O	%	0.000559	na	na	na	0.000559	na	na		
		CO	%	0.0003111	na	na	na	0.0003111	na	na		
6	Biodiesel production (1 ton of fleshings)	Pretreatment	kWh/kg	0.03	X	0.03	X	X	X	X	X	(Bhagwat et al. 2015)
		NH ₄ Cl	%	varies	X	1	X	X	X	X	X	(Sandhya et al. 2016)
		HCl	%	varies	X	2	X	X	X	X	X	(Sousa et al. 2017)
		H ₂ O	%	varies	X	15	X	X	X	X	X	(Sandhya, Abinandan et al. 2016)
		Fat- Drying	%	varies	X	25	X	X	X	X	X	(Sandhya et al. 2016)
		Heat	MJ/kg	0.396	X	0.396	X	X	X	X	X	
		Energy	kWh/kg	0.01	X	0.01	X	X	X	X	X	
		Esterification										
		Heat	MJ/kg	0.17594	X	0.17594	X	X	X	X	X	(Dufour and Iribarren 2012)
		Energy	kWh/kg	0.028	X	0.028	X	X	X	X	X	
		H ₂ SO ₄	%	0.2	X	0.2	X	X	X	X	X	(Kubendran et al. 2017)
		Methanol	%	0.15543	X	0.15543	X	X	X	X	X	(Saranya and Ramachandra 2020)

		Transesterification										
		Heat	MJ/kg	1.73333	X	1.73333	X	X	X	X	X	(Dufour and Iribarren 2012)
		Energy	kWh/kg	0.03	X	0.03	X	X	X	X	X	
		Glycerin	%	0.11564	X	0.11564	X	X	X	X	X	
		Methanol	%	0.01811	X	0.01811	X	X	X	X	X	(Sousa et al. 2017)
		Washing										
		Dry-washing	kWh/kg	0.0874	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	(Alamsyah and Loebis 2014)
		Wet washing	kWh/kg	0.378	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
utilization of chrome shavings as leather sheet and buffing dust as leather sheet												
7	Chrome shavings as a leather board	Waste	kg	1000	na	na	na	1000	na	na	na	(Senthil et al. 2023)
		Raw water	kg	2000	na	na	na	2000	na	na	na	
		Papermill sludge	kg	1000	na	na	na	1000	na	na	na	
		Ethylene glycol	%	4%	na	na	na	4%	na	na	na	
		H ₂ SO ₄	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Natural rubber latex	kg	80	na	na	na	600	na	na	na	
		The final weight of the sheet	%	16	na	na	na	16	na	na	na	(Senthil et al. 2015)
		Energy consumption (mixer)	kWh/kg	0.0055	na	na	na	0.0055	na	na	na	(Adusei-Bonsu et al. 2021)
		Energy consumption at 800 psi and 1500 psi	kWh/kg	0.046	na	na	na	0.046	na	na	na	(Salsabila et al. 2021)
	kWh/kg	0.092	na	na	na	0.092	na	na	na			
8	Gelatin production from raw trimmings	Waste	kg	1000	1000	na	na	na	na	na	na	Assumption
		Transport	km	20	20	na	na	na	na	na	na	Assumption
		Washing (water)	kg	varies	2000	na	na	na	na	na	na	(Shakil et al. 2019)
		Pretreatment	kWh/ton	45	45	na	na	na	na	na	na	(Xavier et al. 2015)
		Soaking										
		Water (5% absorp.)	kg	4000	4000	na	na	na	na	na	na	(Shakil et al. 2019)
		Wetting agent	kg	2.5	2.5	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Sodium carbonate	%	3	3	na	na	na	na	na	na	
Preservatives	%	2.5	2.5	na	na	na	na	na	na			

		Washing	kg	2000	2000	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Liming										
		Water (5% absorp.)	kg	4000	4000	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Sodium sulfide	%	4	4	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Lime	%	6	6	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Liming auxiliary	%	0.5	0.5	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		HCl	%	4	4	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		pH		1.5	1.5	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Deliming										
		Water (5% absorp.)	kg	2000	2000	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Ammonium sulphate	%	2	2	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Ammonium chloride	%	1	1	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Melting	kWh/kg	calculated	0.03	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Temp.	°C	140	140	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Drying under sun	days	7 to 12	7 to 12	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Grinding	kWh/ton	22	22	na	na	na	na	na	na	http://lmengineering.de/zerkleinerungstechnik.html
		Output as gelatin	%	46	46	na	na	na	na	na	na	(Shakil et al. 2019)
9	Keratin production from hair waste	Input	kg	1000	na	na	1000	na	na	na	na	Assumption
		Transport	km	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	Assumption
		Shredding	kWh/kg	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	
		Stirring at 70°C	kWh/kg	0.001867	na	na	0.001867	na	na	na	na	https://www.ika.com/en/Products-LabEq/Magnetic-Stirrers-pg188/L-MAG-Industry-stirrer-20014226/Technical-Data-cptd.html
		Normal cooling	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na
		Filteration	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	na	

		Industrial centrifuge		0.001	na	na	0.001	na	na	na	na	(Szepešy and Thorwid 2018)
		Deep freezing	°C	(-80°C)	na	na	(-80°C)	na	na	na	na	https://www.bluetipower.com/blogs/news/how-many-watts-does-a-freezer-use#:~:text=Daily%20Consumption%20(WWh)%20%3D%20Wattage.to%2025%20kWh%20every%20month.
		Output	gm/l,	40	na	na	40	na	na	na	na	(Da Souza, Benvenuti et al. 2022)